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Thesis: Doctor in Systems Control

LNET: An Approximation Structure for Discrete Nonlinear Systems

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Preface

This thesis is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor in Systems Control at the Universidad Nacional del Sur, and has not been previously submitted for any other degree at this or any other university. It contains the results of research carried out under the supervision of Dr. Osvaldo Agamennoni.

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*To Mariela, my companion, friend, and wife.
But if a picture is worth more than a thousand
words, what then, Petisa, would be sufficient
to express a feeling?*

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Abstract

This thesis introduces the LNet approximation structure, which is composed of a set of discrete Laguerre systems nonlinearly combined by a single hidden layer Perceptron. This structure is capable of approximating systems that can be characterized as discrete, causal, time-invariant nonlinear systems possessing a certain type of continuity called fading memory. This form of continuity provides the theoretical basis for using the so-called Lipschitz coefficients to evaluate the number of Laguerre systems. The number of hidden layer neurons is estimated by a pruning technique based on the singular value decomposition of a certain transformation of the data. The complete identification methodology developed is illustrated through several examples in which the approximation results obtained are compared with those of other models. The first of these examples consists of a discrete nonlinear system, followed by a nonlinear echo cancellation case in a telephone line. As the last example, the proposed methodology is applied to modeling a binary alcohol distillation column and to its control by means of a predictive control strategy. The thesis concludes with a discussion of future research directions in this area.

General Notation.

The following establishes the general notation. A variable u represents either a sequence or a scalar value depending on context. In the case of a sequence, its value at a given time k is denoted $u(k)$. Vectors are denoted in bold lowercase \mathbf{x} and matrices in bold uppercase \mathbf{A} . Scalar functions use italic lowercase f and vector-valued functions bold lowercase \mathbf{f} . Functionals F and operators N use italic uppercase. Functional spaces are denoted, for example, as $\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{U})$.

Various

$\mathbf{x}(k)$: discrete states of the system at time instant k .

$u(k)$: value of the input at time instant k .

$y(k)$: value of the output at time instant k .

u : input sequence.

y : output sequence.

\mathbf{f} : state transition function.

$\tilde{\mathbf{f}}$: approximation of the state transition function \mathbf{f} .

h : output function.

\tilde{h} : approximation of the output function h .

\mathfrak{z} : complex variable of the \mathcal{Z} -transform.

$\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{c}$: description of the SISO linear system.

\mathbf{Z} : data matrix filtered by the Laguerre systems.

\mathbf{X}_o : matrix \mathbf{Z} propagated through the hidden layer.

$\mathbf{U}_o, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_o, \mathbf{V}_o$: $\mathbf{X}_o = \mathbf{U}_o^T \cdot \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_o \cdot \mathbf{V}_o$, singular value decomposition of the matrix \mathbf{X}_o .

$c_{m_0 m_1 \dots m_n}$: coefficients of the Wiener series.

s : output of a neuron before the nonlinearity ϕ .

o : output of a neuron after the nonlinearity ϕ .

ϕ : nonlinearity of the neuron.

ϕ : nonlinearity of the layer.

α : affine transformation of the neuron.

$\boldsymbol{\alpha}$: affine transformation of the layer.

g : continuous function.

$k_m(\cdot, \cdot, \dots, \cdot)$: kernels of the Volterra series.

$a_{l_0 l_1 \dots l_m}$: coefficients of the Volterra series.

$l_p(t)$: continuous Laguerre systems of order p .

$l_n(k)$: discrete Laguerre systems of order n .

$ph_{m_n}(\cdot)$: Hermite polynomials.

$vv_p(t)$: auxiliary variable representing the convolution of the input signal $u(t)$ with the Laguerre system $l_p(t)$.

λ : Lipschitz coefficients.

$\mathbf{G}_i(\cdot)$: matrix transfer function.

B_r : ball of radius r .

Γ_{B_r} : set of continuous functions in B_r with finite gradient extension.

Constants.

nc : number of hidden layers of a Perceptron.

no_i : number of neurons of the i -th hidden layer.

lm : memory length.

m : number of Laguerre systems in the LNet structure.

n_u : number of input u terms used in a recursive equation.

n_y : number of output y terms used in a recursive equation.

n_L : number of Laguerre systems in the expansion of a linear system.

np : number of input-output data pairs $[u(k), y(k)]$ available.

c_λ : bound on the Lipschitz coefficients.

k_{lip} : Lipschitz constant.

r_o : rank of the matrix \mathbf{X}_o .

r : memory length of the impulse response $h_{cp_i}(k)$.

Impulse Responses and Regressors

$hlin(k)$: impulse response of the linear system.

$hgc_i(k)$: impulse response of the general cascade block model for the i -th section.

$hcp_i(k)$: impulse response of the parallel cascade model for the i -th section.

$\mathbf{u}_L(k)$: es el vector de los sistemas de Laguerre.

$\mathbf{u}_{nu}(k)$: input regressor vector of the system up to order $k - nu$.

$\mathbf{y}_{ny}(k)$: output regressor vector of the system up to order $k - ny$.

$\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k)$: output regressor vector of the model up to order $k - ny$.

Operators and Functionals.

$P[u](k)$: truncation operator applied to input u at time k .

$q^{-1}[\cdot]$: unit delay operator.

$q^\tau[\cdot]$: delay operator of τ samples.

$R^{lm}[\cdot]$: delay line operator of order lm .

$N_i[\cdot]$: single-layer transformation operator.

$L_i[u](k)$: i -th Laguerre operator applied to input u at time k .

$G_i[u]$: functional associated with the i -th Laguerre operator applied to input u .

$N[u](k)$: discrete nonlinear operator applied to u at time k .

$F[u]$: functional associated with the causal shift-invariant operator N applied to input u .

Spaces.

\mathbb{R}^n : Euclidean space of dimension n .

\mathbb{Z} : space of integers.

l^∞ : space of bounded sequences, equipped with the supremum norm.

$\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{U})$: space of continuous functions on the compact set \mathbf{U} .

$\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{U})$: space spanned by polynomials on the compact set \mathbf{U} .

$\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{U})$: space spanned by single hidden layer Perceptrons on the compact set \mathbf{U} .

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter presents the general problem of obtaining models through an identification process based on input-output data. First, general considerations are set out clarifying what is meant by system, inputs, outputs, models, etc., followed by a possible classification of model types. It is then shown that identifying the internal representations of linear models yields infinite-memory models, while identifying their external representation produces finite-memory models. These concepts are extended to nonlinear systems with fading memory. For systems that can be characterized as nonlinear, with fading memory, and shift-invariant, the convenience of identifying their external representation through the proposed LNet approximation structure is shown. The LNet structure is capable of approximating such systems arbitrarily well and uniformly, via a nonlinear combination of Laguerre systems implemented through a single hidden layer Perceptron. The chapter concludes with a general overview of the remaining chapters of the thesis.

1.1 Systems and Models

In general terms, a *system* is an object (or collection of objects) upon which various classes of variables interact and from which certain properties are to be studied. *Outputs* are the observable signals produced by the system that are of interest, while the variables that can be manipulated to affect the system are called *inputs*. A *model* is a tool used to study and/or explain certain properties of the system without having to perform experiments on it. The *experimentation* process is the procedure by which the

cause-effect relationships of the system are revealed. The knowledge obtained through experimentation is then used to postulate hypotheses that will form part of the models. In general, the degree of accuracy of a model depends on its intended future use. However, no model is sufficiently exact and/or general to describe all aspects of the behavior of the system under study. It should be noted that a model, a law, a theory, or a paradigm can only partially explain a phenomenon, and remains valid until another (model, law, theory, or paradigm) supersedes it. While it is unlikely that a model exactly reproduces the behavior of a system, what can be expected is that it reproduces certain behaviors acceptably under certain conditions, and that it is capable of reproducing comparable results under analogous conditions. This speaks to the reproducibility of experimentation, a fundamental step in any scientific theory. In this way, each chosen model is valid for the conditions under which the experimentation was performed, which constitute its *domain of application or validity*. Validation of the model, law, theory, or paradigm is usually obtained by contrast with reality.

In general, science attempts to infer models from observations and study their properties. Such models may be of a more or less formal character, whether hypotheses, laws of nature, paradigms, etc. However, they all share the characteristic of attempting to associate what is observed with a pattern that explains it. Depending on the qualities of the system being studied, the precision requirements, and the modeling tools used, models will exhibit characteristics—many of which are dichotomous—according to the following model classification.

1.2 Taxonomy of Models

The value of this classification is orientational and does not claim to be conclusive, since there exists a great diversity of systems (chaotic, etc.) that either cannot be categorized according to it or may be classified according to other criteria.

Linear/Nonlinear.

Linear model: expresses linear relationships among its variables. The superposition principle is valid. Ex. $dy(t)/dt = ay(t) + bu(t)$

Nonlinear model: expresses nonlinear relationships among its variables; the superposition principle does not hold. Ex. $dy(t)/dt = a\sqrt{y(t)} + bu(t)$

Lumped/Distributed Parameters:

Lumped-parameter model: the system is described by a set of ordinary differential equations. The parameters are expressed through a finite (lumped) set of values. Ex. $dy/dt = ay(t) + bu(t)$

Distributed-parameter model: the system is described by a set of partial differential equations. The parameters are expressed through an infinite (distributed) set of values, such as distributions, concentration profiles, etc. Ex. $\alpha(t) \partial^2 y(t, x) / dx^2 = \partial y(t, x) / \partial t$

Deterministic/Stochastic.

Deterministic model: the system is described by a set of equations in which the events that occur can be characterized individually. Ex. Thermodynamic law of ideal gases.

Stochastic model: the system is described by a set of equations in which variables can only be characterized by their statistical properties, such as probability distribution, mean, variance, etc. Ex. Brownian motion in a gas.

Continuous/Discrete Time.

Continuous-time model: describes systems where variables depend continuously on time. Described by sets of differential equations. Ex. $dy(t) / dt = ay(t) + bu(t)$, $t \in [0, \infty)$

Discrete-time model: the variables of these models are only defined at discrete time instants. Described by difference equations. Ex. $y(k+1) = ay(k) + bu(k)$, $k \in [0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, \infty)$

Time-Invariant/Time-Varying.

Time-invariant model: describes systems where the relationship between variables and parameters is constant. Consequently, the response to a given input does not depend on the time at which it is applied. Ex. $dy(t) / dt = ay(t) + bu(t)$

Time-varying model: describes systems where the relationship between variables and parameters depends on time. Ex. $dy(t) / dt = a(t)y(t) + bu(t)$, $a(t) = a_0 \sin(5t)$

External/Internal.

External or input-output model: describes the system by establishing a direct relationship between its inputs and outputs. Ex. the impulse response of a linear system.

Internal or input-state-output model: describes the system by establishing the relationships between input variables and internal variables or states, and between these states and the outputs. The state-space description is the typical characterization of this class.

Causal.

Causal model: models that respond to a cause-effect relationship. In other words, the outputs of the model depend only on its prior evolution and not on future events.

Once the type of model required for a particular application has been defined, there are basically two very different paths for obtaining it: theoretical modeling and system identification.

1.2.1 Rigorous Modeling or Identification?

In general, a system is constituted by elements, each of which involves a transformation and/or a transport of mass, energy, and/or information. A mathematical model reflects part of these processes, only when the properties of interest have been abstracted from the system. Rigorous theoretical modeling provides techniques for setting up equations that express the dynamic behavior of the system from the physical and phenomenological laws of its components. In engineering applications, the most commonly used laws include mass and energy balances, Newton's laws, Coulomb friction law, Bernoulli's ideal fluid law, etc. These laws model the behavior of certain constituent sub-parts of the system under study, which combined form the total model, proceeding from the particular to the general. As noted above, a mathematical model may be a simple linear differential equation with lumped parameters, or it could be a complex system of nonlinear partial differential equations with time and space dependent parameters. This complexity often imposes several obstacles when obtaining models in this way:

- The assumptions required to obtain the model may be too restrictive or unrealistic, making it impossible to capture the essential behavior of the system.
- Some parameters are often very difficult to measure or, worse, entirely unknown.
- Very complex models require solving a large set of differential equations, which usually constitute the bottleneck during numerical integration.

The alternative approach to obtaining a mathematical model of a dynamic system consists of building it directly from data obtained through an experimentation process. The process of generating a model from the data obtained from the system is called *identification*. The characteristics of models obtained through identification techniques vary according to the type of approach used; it is useful to clarify some concepts. These

will be illustrated for the linear case, with the respective extensions then made to the nonlinear case.

1.3 Approximation of Linear Systems

Let a system that admits being modeled as a linear, discrete, time-invariant system with a scalar input u and a scalar output y that at discrete time instant k take the values $u(k)$ and $y(k)$ respectively, as in Figure 1.1. Let a state-space description be:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(k+1) &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{b}u(k) \\ y(k) &= \mathbf{c}\mathbf{x}(k) \end{aligned}, \quad (1.1)$$

where $k \in (-\infty, \dots, -1, 0, 1, \dots, \infty)$, $\mathbf{x}(k) = [x_1(k), x_2(k), \dots, x_n(k)]$ represents the n states, \mathbf{x}_0 is the initial state, with \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{b} , and \mathbf{c} of dimensions $(n \times n)$, $(n \times 1)$, and $(1 \times n)$ respectively. For clarity of exposition we treat a single-input single-output system. With appropriate considerations, analogous results can be generalized to multi-input multi-output systems.

Figure 1.1: Schematic Representation of the System.

An alternative characterization of 1.1 is obtained through the *impulse response* $hlin(k)$ (or weight function):

$$y(k) = \sum_{\tau=0}^{\infty} hlin(\tau) u(k-\tau). \quad (1.2)$$

Knowing $\{hlin(\tau)\}_{\tau=0}^{\infty}$ and $u(l)$ for all $l \leq k$ allows one to determine the output $y(l)$, $l \leq k$ for any input. *Consequently, the impulse response provides a complete characterization of the system.* Since this impulse response is infinite, it is useful to consider more compact recursive forms that avoid having to use the infinite terms of $hlin(k)$. Accordingly,

equation 1.2 can be expressed as

$$y(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_y} a_i y(k-i) + \sum_{j=0}^{n_u} b_j u(k-j), \quad (1.3)$$

where the parameters a_i and b_j have orders n_y and n_u respectively, $n_y > n_u$. Applying the \mathcal{Z} -transform to expression 1.3 yields the following rational function:

$$y(\mathfrak{z}) = \frac{b_0 + b_1 \mathfrak{z}^{-1} + \dots + b_{n_u} \mathfrak{z}^{-n_u}}{1 + a_1 \mathfrak{z}^{-1} + a_2 \mathfrak{z}^{-2} \dots + a_{n_y} \mathfrak{z}^{-n_y}} u(\mathfrak{z}), \quad (1.4)$$

where $y(\mathfrak{z}) = \mathcal{Z}[y(k)]$, $u(\mathfrak{z}) = \mathcal{Z}[u(k)]$. This polynomial quotient is a linear operator in the complex variable \mathfrak{z} relating the input transform to the output transform. The *zeros* are the roots of the numerator polynomial of 1.4 and the *poles* are the roots of the denominator polynomial in the usual sense. If we assume the numerator and denominator polynomials of equation 1.4 are coprime,¹ the following state-space representation is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(k+1) &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{b}u(k) \\ y(k) &= \mathbf{c}\mathbf{x}(k) \end{aligned}, \quad (1.5)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(k) = [x_1(k), x_2(k), \dots, x_{n_y}(k)]$, $k \in (-\infty, \dots, -1, 0, 1, \dots, \infty)$ represents the n_y states; $\mathbf{A} : (n_y \times n_y)$, $\mathbf{b} : (n_y \times 1)$, and $\mathbf{c} : (1 \times n_y)$. The corresponding matrix values are:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -a_1 & -a_2 & \cdots & -a_{n_y-1} & -a_{n_y} \\ 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{b} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{c} = [0^{(1 \times (n_y - n_u))}, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{n_u}]$$

where $0^{(1 \times (n_y - n_u))}$ is a zero row vector of length $(n_y - n_u)$.

Four different possible characterizations of a linear, discrete, shift-invariant model have been presented. On one hand, there is the representation via an infinite convolution sum 1.2 that requires no prior knowledge, constituting an external characterization

¹Coprime polynomials are those that share no common factors.

of the system. On the other, there are the recursive equation characterizations 1.3, the description via a linear operator in the complex variable \mathfrak{z} 1.4, and the state-space description 1.5. These descriptions require certain internal knowledge of the system, manifested in the order of the recursions, the number of poles and zeros, and/or the order of the state-space system. Given the equivalence among representations 1.3, 1.4, and 1.5, we classify these as internal representations of the linear system. A model is said to have *finite memory* if its current output $\tilde{y}(k)$ depends on a finite set of values; otherwise it is said to have infinite memory. We will now show that approximating the internal representation of a linear system yields an infinite-memory model, while approximating the external representation yields a finite-memory model.

1.3.1 Internal Representation of Linear Systems

We will see that approximating the system described by a recursive equation such as 1.3 leads to an IIR (Infinite Impulse Response) model (Figures 1.2a and 1.2b). The family of models known as ARMAX, AR, ARAMAX, etc., as found in the literature [39, Ljung], derives from this type of approximation. We define two operators of great utility

Figure 1.2: Different Types of Models.

in subsequent developments: $q^\tau [\cdot]$ is the τ -sample delay operator defined by

$$\begin{aligned} q^\tau [u](k) &= u(k + \tau) \\ q^{-\tau} [u](k) &= u(k - \tau) \end{aligned} \quad (1.6)$$

and $R^{lm} [\cdot]$ is the delay line operator of order lm defined by

$$R^{lm} [u](k) = [u(k), u(k-1), \dots, u(k-lm+1)]^T. \quad (1.7)$$

We write $q^\tau u(k)$ and $R^{lm}u(k)$ in place of $q^\tau [u](k)$ and $R^{lm}[u](k)$ respectively, whenever clear from context. The unit delay operator is denoted q^{-1} . Based on these operators we define the input regressor vectors

$$\mathbf{u}_{nu}(k) = R^{nu}[u](k) = [u(k), \dots, u(k - nu)]^T \quad (1.8)$$

and the output regressor vectors,

$$\mathbf{y}_{ny}(k) = R^{ny}[y](k) = [y(k - 1), \dots, y(k - n_y)]^T \quad (1.9)$$

which allows equation 1.3 to be expressed in a more compact form

$$y(k) = \bar{\mathbf{a}}^T \mathbf{y}_{ny}(k) + \bar{\mathbf{b}}^T \mathbf{u}_{nu}(k) \quad (1.10)$$

with parameter vectors $\bar{\mathbf{a}} = [a_1, \dots, a_{n_y}]^T$ and $\bar{\mathbf{b}} = [b_0, \dots, b_{n_u}]^T$.

Ideally one would like to generate the estimated value $\tilde{y}(k)$ of $y(k)$ as in the scheme of Figure 1.2b:

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \tilde{\mathbf{b}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k) + \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^T \mathbf{u}_{nu}(k),$$

using the model output regressor vector

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k) = [\tilde{y}(k - 1), \dots, \tilde{y}(k - n_y)]^T, \quad (1.11)$$

with $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}$ the estimated values of $\bar{\mathbf{a}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{b}}$ respectively. To adjust the model parameters one minimizes a cost function of the error $e = y(k) - \tilde{y}(k)$. In the scheme of Figure 1.2b, the outputs $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k)$ are used to generate the next value $\tilde{y}(k)$, introducing feedback since the model is adjusted based on $\mathbf{u}_{nu}(k)$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k)$. Unfortunately, the estimation problem posed in this form is highly nonlinear and has serious stability issues [68].

A possible solution consists of using the structure of Figure 1.2a, which is equivalent to linearizing the parameter estimation problem by using the true outputs

$[y(k-1), \dots, y(k-n_y)]:$

$$\begin{aligned}
 e(k) &= y(k) - \tilde{y}(k) \\
 &= y(k) - \tilde{\mathbf{b}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k) - \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^T \mathbf{u}_{nu}(k) \\
 &= (\bar{\mathbf{b}} - \tilde{\mathbf{b}})^T \mathbf{y}_{ny}(k) + (\bar{\mathbf{a}} - \tilde{\mathbf{a}})^T \mathbf{u}(k)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.12}$$

As a result, the estimation problem can be solved using least squares in a straightforward manner. Both models in Figures 1.2a and 1.2b use delayed output values ($\mathbf{y}_{ny}(k)$ or $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k)$ respectively), generating a continuous dependence of $\tilde{y}(k)$ on the initial state, which is why they are called infinite-memory models. We will now show that approximating the external representation of a linear system yields a finite-memory model.

1.3.2 External Representation of Linear Systems

FIR

Another option for characterizing system 1.5 consists of taking a finite number n_u of terms of its impulse response. This is equivalent to truncating the sum 1.2, estimating only the first n_u terms of $\{hlin(\tau)\}_{\tau=0}^{n_u-1}$, leading to a finite-memory model called FIR (Finite Impulse Response, Figure 1.2c). In fact, a FIR model is also obtained by eliminating the recursion in 1.10 by setting $\bar{\mathbf{a}}^T = 0$:

$$y(k) = \bar{\mathbf{b}}^T \mathbf{u}_{nu}(k), \tag{1.13}$$

with \mathbf{u}_{nu} as in 1.8 for n_u the filter order. It is easy to see that the external approximation of this system has an infinite series representation that, when truncated, yields a finite-memory model. Clearly, to improve the FIR model approximation it is necessary to increase the order n_u , which implies increasing the number of parameters that must be identified. In this sense, the order of a FIR filter for the same realization is approximately one order higher than that of an IIR filter. However, this type of model is very easy to identify: the estimates obtained are global minima, the algorithms are stable, and the models are very easy to use in simulation.

Alternatively, FIR-type models can be viewed from the perspective of functional

approximations as:

$$y(k) = \sum_{i=0}^{n_u} b_i q^i [u](k). \quad (1.14)$$

It can be seen that the system is expanded in an orthonormal basis formed by unit delays. The unit delay operator q^{-1} has a memory of only one value, which would explain the large number of terms needed to approximate certain systems. Moreover, its use is not adequate for short sampling periods [46]. An alternative is to use another operator, such as Laguerre systems, which—having greater memory—reduces the number of terms involved in the approximation.

Laguerre

The approximation of systems 1.5 based on Laguerre systems is well known in the literature [75, 76]. The set of systems can be expressed in the complex domain as:

$$L_i(\mathfrak{z}) = \mathfrak{z}^{-nd} \sqrt{(1-a^2)} T \frac{\mathfrak{z}}{\mathfrak{z}-a} \left[\frac{1-a\mathfrak{z}}{\mathfrak{z}-a} \right]^i, \quad i: 0, \dots, \infty, \quad (1.15)$$

where:

$L_i(\mathfrak{z})$: is the \mathcal{Z} -transform of $l_i(k)$, the system of order i .

a : the generating pole such that $|a| < 1$, ensuring stability.

T : sampling time. When the system is discrete, $T = 1$.

nd : represents a pure delay of nd samples.

This set of systems represents a generalization of those presented in [9, 75, 76] since they include a delay of nd samples. In [75] strictly proper systems are treated, so the systems defined by 1.15 coincide with those presented there when $nd = 1$. It is known that linear systems with pure delays can be modeled by Laguerre systems [40, 55]. However, when the system is discrete, it is more useful to separate the delay as an exact number of samples and approximate the rest of the system using the mentioned expansions. The inclusion of the term modeling the pure delay has a relatively simple explanation: suppose one wishes to approximate a linear discrete system that is a pure one-sample delay, i.e., with impulse response $hlin(k) = \{0, 1\}$. This simple system,

so easy to approximate using a unit delay operator q^{-1} , requires an excessive number of Laguerre operators. Such a delay is easily detectable via correlation analysis and is much simpler to model separately than through the full Laguerre system expansion. The following example clarifies this point.

Example 1. *Suppose one wishes to approximate a continuous function $g(x) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on the segment $[-\pi, \pi]$ using two different approximators. One is the polynomial*

$$p(x) = \sum_{i=0}^m cp_i x^i, \quad (1.16)$$

with $cp_i \in \mathbb{R}$, and the other is the Fourier series

$$sf(x) = \sum_{i=0}^m af_i \sin(2\pi ix) + \sum_{i=0}^m bf_i \cos(2\pi ix), \quad (1.17)$$

with $af_i, bf_i \in \mathbb{R}$. In this way, the function $g(x)$ can be expressed as

$$g(x) \cong p(x),$$

where \cong means approximately equal, for $x \in [-\pi, \pi]$, which is equivalent to saying that the set $\{1, x^2, x^3, \dots\}$ forms a basis in $[-\pi, \pi]$. Similarly, it is possible to establish that

$$g(x) \cong sf(x),$$

for $x \in [-\pi, \pi]$. It is well known that the set of functions $\{\sin(2\pi ix), \cos(2\pi ix)\}$, $i : 0, \dots, \infty$, also forms a basis in $[-\pi, \pi]$. That is, both the polynomial of equation 1.16 and the Fourier series of equation 1.17 have similar approximation capabilities for continuous functions in $[-\pi, \pi]$. However, if $g(x) = \sin(2\pi x)$ is chosen, the number of polynomial terms required is large compared to the single term $\sin(2\pi x)$ needed in a Fourier series. Similar results arise when approximating $g(x) = x^2$ by a Fourier series, compared to the single element x^2 needed by a polynomial. Concretely, whenever a function belonging to one basis must be approximated by elements of another basis with different characteristics, the number of required terms is generally large. Both the set $\{q^i\}_{i=0}^{\infty}$ and $\{L_i(\cdot)\}_{i=0}^{\infty}$ form orthonormal bases for $l^2(\mathbb{Z}_+)$, which explains, following the previous reasoning, the difficulties in expressing elements of one basis in the other. ■

By a slight abuse of notation, equation 1.15 can be expressed in terms of the unit delay operator q^{-1} in a widely used form:

$$L_i(q^{-1}) = q^{-nd} \frac{\sqrt{(1-a^2)T}}{1-aq^{-1}} \left[\frac{q^{-1}-a}{1-aq^{-1}} \right]^i, \quad i = 0, \dots, \infty. \quad (1.18)$$

It can be seen that these systems are generated by a basic low-pass section

$$L_0(q^{-1}) = \frac{\sqrt{(1-a^2)T}}{1-aq^{-1}},$$

to which all-pass sections of the form $\left(\frac{q^{-1}-a}{1-aq^{-1}} \right)$ are added in cascade. In this way each new system can be expressed in terms of the previous one in a simple recursive form

$$L_i(q^{-1}) = L_{i-1}(q^{-1}) \left(\frac{q^{-1}-a}{1-aq^{-1}} \right).$$

Using these systems as a basis, a strictly proper linear system can be represented (see for example [75]) by equation 1.18 with $nd = 1$, as:

$$y(k) = \sum_{i=0}^{n_L} b_i L_i[u](k). \quad (1.19)$$

With a proper selection of a , approximations up to one order smaller than those achievable with a FIR can be obtained, comparable to IIR approximations ($n_u \gg n_L \simeq n_y$). Wahlberg [75] suggests that this is because the operator of the Laguerre systems has more memory than the unit delay operator used in a FIR. The advantages are significant both from the approximation and stability perspectives. When used in an adaptive identification scheme, stability is easily ensured by simply controlling that $|a| < 1$. Moreover, these models can be used in simulation for arbitrarily long time horizons.

On one hand, we have seen that approximating the internal representation of a linear discrete system yields infinite-memory models called IIR. These models are very economical in the number of terms they use to represent a given system. On the other hand, approximating the external representation of a linear discrete system yields a finite-memory model called FIR. Another option is to use Laguerre systems for the approximation. As with a FIR, it is possible both to simulate the system for arbitrarily long time horizons and to improve the approximation by simply increasing the model

order. By carefully selecting the pole value, approximations whose number of terms is comparable to an IIR can be achieved. The following section presents analogous concepts developed for nonlinear systems with fading memory.

1.4 Approximation of NLS with Fading Memory

Given the inherent complexity of nonlinear systems, it is usually necessary to restrict the field of study to a subclass of them. Here we treat the subclass of discrete nonlinear systems possessing fading memory. We begin by considering the *Internal* representation of discrete nonlinear systems, known as the *Input-State-Output* representation:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(k+1) &= \mathbf{f}[\mathbf{x}(k), u(k)] \\ y(k) &= h[\mathbf{x}(k)] \end{aligned}, \quad (1.20)$$

$k \in (-\infty, \dots, -1, 0, 1, \dots, \infty)$ where $u(k)$, $\mathbf{x}(k)$, and $y(k)$ represent elements of the input, state, and output sequences at time instant k ; \mathbf{x}_0 is the initial state. Let l^∞ be the space of bounded sequences equipped with the supremum norm

$$\|u\|_\infty = \sup_k |u(k)|.$$

An element of this space is a sequence of values u that at time k takes the value $u(k)$. However, approximating a nonlinear system on such a general set is a difficult task. A more realistic view consists of selecting a subspace \mathbf{K} such that

$$\mathbf{K} \triangleq \{u \in l^\infty \mid \|u\|_\infty < m_1, m_1 > 0\}. \quad (1.21)$$

The only requirement is that the input be bounded within a region. As mentioned above, this subspace constitutes the domain of application or validity of the model. Each element of a sequence belongs to a finite-dimensional vector space: $u(k) \in \mathbf{U}$, the input space; $\mathbf{x}(k) \in \mathbf{X}$, the state space; and $y(k) \in \mathbf{Y}$, the output space. The functions \mathbf{f} and h are static nonlinear transformations defined as $\mathbf{f} : \mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$ and $h : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$. For a single-input single-output system, $\mathbf{U} \subset \mathbb{R}$, $\mathbf{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, $\mathbf{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}$ with state vector

$\mathbf{x}(k) = [x_1(k), x_2(k), \dots, x_n(k)]$. A system Σ is then characterized by the set

$$\Sigma = (\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{f}, h, x_0). \quad (1.22)$$

The functions \mathbf{f} and h in 1.20 describe the system from the viewpoint of its state variables or internal representation. To express the system in this way requires a large amount of physical knowledge of the system, i.e., knowledge of its states. We now consider the nonlinear equivalent of equation 1.3:

$$y(k) = g([y(k-1), \dots, y(k-n_y)], [u(k-1), \dots, u(k-n_u)]), \quad (1.23)$$

or by 1.9 and 1.8 as

$$y(k) = g(\mathbf{y}_{ny}(k), \mathbf{u}_{nu}(k)), \quad (1.24)$$

where $g(\cdot)$ is a memoryless nonlinear function. This type of model, called NARMAX [50] by analogy with the linear ARMAX case, will be considered as an internal representation of 1.20.

To characterize the external representation of system 1.22, we consider the input-output operator $N : l^\infty \rightarrow l^\infty$ associated with this system:

$$y(k) = N[u](k). \quad (1.25)$$

This operator may not exist for the full generality of discrete nonlinear systems, unlike the linear case for which the \mathcal{Z} -transform is defined. However, for systems with fading memory this operator can be approximated. We now define what is meant by the approximation of this operator and by fading memory.

Given a system and its model, one intuitively expects their outputs to remain close. We say that a model uniformly approximates a system on a subset \mathbf{K} (see equation 1.21) of the input with $\varepsilon > 0$, if for the entire length of the input sequence u in \mathbf{K} , the output remains within ε . The representation of equation 1.20 is general and describes a wide diversity of discrete nonlinear systems, not all of which can be uniformly approximated. As a specific example, consider an autonomous nonlinear system with multiple equilibrium regions. An inaccurate model may converge to state-space regions that do not coincide with those of the system. If the initial conditions lie near the

boundary between two different regions, the model may converge to a different region than that of the original system. A class of systems that can be approximated under the above criteria is the so-called class of fading-memory systems. Stable linear systems are good examples of fading-memory systems: for a constant input sequence, the output converges asymptotically to the corresponding steady-state value regardless of the initial conditions. Other examples include cascades of linear dynamic systems with memoryless nonlinear systems,² such as Wiener and Hammerstein models. The concept of fading memory is strictly related to input-output properties. This defines a form of continuity in the input-output operator associated with the system. We therefore define the concept of fading memory from the viewpoint of function continuity. A function is said to be continuous if nearby elements in the domain have nearby images. Similarly, a system is said to be continuous on a subset \mathbf{K} of the input sequence space if input sequences that are close in some sense produce output sequences that are close. The notion of closeness is determined by a norm. In this sense, Σ is said to be a *causal continuous* on \mathbf{K} if, given $\varepsilon > 0$, for each $u, v \in \mathbf{K}$ there exists $\delta(\varepsilon, u) > 0$ such that

$$\|u - v\|_* < \delta \implies |N[u](0) - N[v](0)| < \varepsilon,$$

where $N[u](k)$ is as in 1.25, and $\|\cdot\|_*$ denotes an arbitrary norm on the input space.

The influence of past inputs on the output in a continuous system is independent of elapsed time: what happened in the remote past has the same influence on the output as what happened recently. On the contrary, for a *causal* fading-memory system, the influence of the input on the output decreases as one goes further into the past. Therefore, a more convenient way to define the norm $\|\cdot\|_*$ of the input space is to use a weighted norm $\|\cdot\|_w$ with the sequence w . This sequence $w : [0, 1, 2, \dots) \rightarrow (0, 1]$, which is non-increasing, non-negative, and satisfies $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} w(k) = 0$, captures the aforementioned influence:

$$\|u\|_w = \sup_{k \leq 0} |u(k)| w(-k).$$

In this sense, a *causal* fading-memory system tends to “forget” its inputs in a well-defined manner over time. In other words, in a fading-memory system, input sequences that are close in their *recent past* (as measured by the norm $\|u\|_w$) produce similar output

²In a memoryless nonlinear system, the output at each time instant is only a function of the input at that same time. Ex.: $y(k) = g(u(k))$

sequences (Figure 1.3). A causal system $\Sigma = (\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{f}, h, x_0)$ has *fading memory* (\mathcal{ME}) on a subset \mathbf{K} 1.21 ([6, 42]), if given $\varepsilon > 0$ and for each $u, v \in \mathbf{K}$, there exists $\delta(\varepsilon, u) > 0$ such that

$$\|u - v\|_w < \delta \implies |N[u](0) - N[v](0)| < \varepsilon. \quad (1.26)$$

The characterization $y(k) = N[u](k)$ constitutes the external representation of a fading-memory system. We will now see that approximating the internal representation of a fading-memory system yields an infinite-memory model, while approximating its external representation yields a finite-memory model.

Figure 1.3: System with Fading Memory.

1.4.1 Internal Representation of Nonlinear Systems

The functions \mathbf{f} and h constitute the internal representation of system 1.20. Obtaining these representations requires a priori physical knowledge of the system—that is, knowing its physical states and having access to them, which in many cases is not feasible. Estimating the inaccessible states is a possible solution, though when the state space dimension is large this approach becomes impractical. Reduced-order estimator theory is applied in these cases; however, since this is a nonlinear problem, ensuring the stability of the observers poses difficulties. An alternative option consists of estimating models of the form 1.23:

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \tilde{g}([\tilde{y}(k-1), \dots, \tilde{y}(k-n_y)], [u(k-1), \dots, u(k-n_u)]),$$

or in vector form by 1.11 and 1.8

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \tilde{g}(\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k), \mathbf{u}_{nu}(k)), \quad (1.27)$$

where $\tilde{g}(\cdot)$ is an approximation of $g(\cdot)$. This model can be used in simulation: given an input sequence $\{u(k+1), u(k+2), \dots\}$ of arbitrary length, it predicts the output sequence $\{\tilde{y}(k+1), \tilde{y}(k+2), \dots\}$ without access to the true system outputs $\{y(k+1), y(k+2), \dots\}$. Narendra [50] calls the scheme of Figure 1.2b the parallel structure and notes the great difficulty of obtaining stable estimators with it; similar considerations can be found in [43]. If the methodology used in the linear case to overcome this difficulty—using the true outputs instead of the model outputs—is extended to the nonlinear case, one arrives at the following formulation (Figure 1.2a):

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \tilde{g}(\mathbf{y}_{ny}(k), \mathbf{u}_{nu}(k)). \quad (1.28)$$

Assume the model was estimated according to 1.28 and that

$$y(k) = \tilde{y}(k) + e(k). \quad (1.29)$$

In certain applications such as predictive control it is necessary to predict the system behavior over arbitrarily long time horizons [44]. Consider the case where it is necessary to predict $\tilde{y}(k+20)$ at time k . In this case, the vector $[y(k+19), \dots, y(k+19-n_y)]$ would be needed. Since the system is causal, $\mathbf{y}_{ny}(k)$ is not available, and thus $[\tilde{y}(k+19), \dots, \tilde{y}(k+19-n_y)]$ would have to be fed back. Taking 1.29 into account, one would obtain

$$[\tilde{y}(k+19) + e(k+19-n_y), \dots, \tilde{y}(k+19-n_y) + e(k+19-n_y)].$$

It can be seen that the error feeds back through the model, producing both a large degradation in prediction performance for more than one step ahead and serious instability problems. It is known that this structure is useful only for one-step-ahead prediction without being extremely unstable or degrading prediction performance. We have seen that using outputs (either $\mathbf{y}_{ny}(k)$ or $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k)$) in the external representation leads to models that depend continuously on the initial values (the nonlinear equivalent of an IIR).

Moreover, the characteristics of both representations are very different: on one hand, with formulation 1.28 the model can be fitted by least squares through simple manipulations, but simulation over only a small number of future instants is possible due to the rapid degradation of predictions from error feedback; on the other hand, when prediction over arbitrarily long horizons is required, a formulation such as 1.27 must be used, but the estimation algorithm is very complex and difficult to implement. A possible solution consists of approximating the external representation of the system.

1.4.2 External Representation of Nonlinear Systems

From equation 1.26 it is clear that if the same input sequence is applied to a fading-memory system but starting from two different initial conditions, the corresponding outputs will converge asymptotically. The asymptotic property of fading memory implies that a system with finite memory has fading memory. In fact, a discrete system whose output depends on only a finite number of past input values (as in a FIR) has fading memory.

Nonlinear FIR

Approximating the external representation of a fading-memory system yields a nonlinear finite-memory model, in which the output at any time instant is a function of only a finite number of past input values. Few results are available proving that a specific type of structure can approximate a given representation of a nonlinear system. For the class of nonlinear fading-memory systems, Boyd and Chua [6] proved that any operator with fading memory can be uniformly approximated by a linear time-invariant operator followed by a polynomial transformation. When the linear dynamic operator is taken as a delay line, a Nonlinear FIR is obtained. Sandberg [60] proved that any causal discrete nonlinear system with approximately finite memory can be approximated arbitrarily well by a set of delayed input values followed by a single hidden layer Perceptron. A single hidden layer Perceptron is an artificial neural network composed of a linear combination of saturated affine linear transformations. The Perceptron is a parametric model capable of modeling a class of continuous functions, being uniformly dense within the space of continuous functions—in other words, it can uniformly approximate any continuous function on a compact set. When the system memory is large, these approxi-

mation schemes are difficult to implement due to the high dimension of the input-output transformation involved. Suppose the system memory were 40: the input vector would then contain values of the 40 past inputs,

$$\mathbf{u}_{40}(k) = [u(k), u(k-1), \dots, u(k-39)],$$

and the output would be expressed as:

$$y(k) = g(\mathbf{u}_{40}(k)) = g([u(k), u(k-1), \dots, u(k-39)]),$$

where $g : R^{40} \rightarrow R$. The results of Stone [71] suggest that if the function is unknown and the dimension is large (e.g., greater than 10), the only possibility for estimating $g(\cdot)$ is to assume great smoothness. If the function is unknown, as in the case treated here, and is not smooth, the total information required to estimate $g(\cdot)$ could be entirely impractical.

Proposed Structure: LNet

As seen for linear systems, approximating the external representation of such systems using functional series leads to a significant reduction in the number of parameters involved. For the LNet structure, the goal is to approximate nonlinear fading-memory models by means of a nonlinear combination of discrete Laguerre systems. This idea follows Wiener [77], in which a continuous nonlinear system is approximated by a polynomial combination of continuous Laguerre systems. The use of a single hidden layer Perceptron to implement the nonlinear combination is justified for several reasons. Among them is the recognized advantage of networks in terms of the number of terms needed to achieve a given approximation, compared to the excessively large number of terms required by a polynomial. Another reason is the inherent pathological behavior of polynomials, which produce excessively large outputs for excessively large inputs. Consequently, the LNet structure allows approximating the class of systems that admit a representation as discrete, causal, time-invariant nonlinear systems possessing fading memory (\mathcal{ME}), in a manner analogous to what was shown in 1.19 for the linear case. It

is expressed as a nonlinear combination of m Laguerre systems 1.15 as:

$$\tilde{y}(k) = NN([L_o[u](k), L_1[u](k), \dots, L_{m-1}[u](k)]), \quad (1.30)$$

where $NN(\cdot)$ represents a single hidden layer Perceptron. Considering no neurons in the hidden layer:

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{no} w2_i \phi(\mathbf{w1}^T \mathbf{u}_L(k) + b1_i) + b2, \quad (1.31)$$

where

$$\mathbf{u}_L(k) = [L_o[u](k), L_1[u](k), \dots, L_{m-1}[u](k)] \quad (1.32)$$

is the Laguerre system vector with $\mathbf{w1}^T \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $b1_i, w2_i, b2 \in R$, and ϕ any continuous sigmoid function.

To determine the structure, one must define the generating pole of the Laguerre systems (a), how many to use (m), and the number of hidden layer neurons. To select the number m of systems, the concept of continuity of the operator associated with the LNet structure is used. Since this operator is continuous it is also Lipschitz bounded. By conveniently defining the so-called Lipschitz coefficients, the number m can be estimated. To evaluate the number of neurons no , a pruning concept is used: starting with a large number of neurons, this number is decreased until an acceptable performance is achieved with the minimum number of neurons. Singular values are used to implement this pruning technique. The resulting model is nonlinear, easily identifiable from input-output data, and can be used in simulation to predict the system behavior over arbitrarily long time horizons.

1.5 Objectives of this Thesis

The objective of this thesis is to present the LNet approximation structure together with a methodology for its use in the identification of discrete nonlinear systems. This structure is composed of a set of discrete Laguerre systems nonlinearly related by a single hidden layer Perceptron. To accomplish the principal objective pursued, the following parts will be developed:

1. Present a general framework for specifying discrete nonlinear systems that incor-

porate neural networks, together with results illustrating the advantage of using neural networks over other types of approximators.

2. Prove that the LNet structure is capable of approximating systems that can be characterized as discrete, causal, time-invariant nonlinear systems with a certain type of continuity called fading memory.
3. Develop an identification methodology for this structure.
4. Show through application examples the advantages of the proposed structure over other identification schemes, both conventional and those containing neural networks, with strong theoretical foundations.

The following presents an outline of the thesis development.

1.6 Thesis Outline

This thesis is structured as follows. Chapter I constitutes the present introduction. Chapter II references various approximation methods and presents a review of artificial neural networks along with a general framework for their notation. Chapter III formulates the approximation results for the proposed structure. Chapter IV develops the structure characterization, training, and model validation methods. Chapter V presents various examples illustrating the application of the proposed modeling methodology, each highlighting specific modeling aspects. The first example illustrates the capability of the modeling methodology to find the correct structure of a discrete nonlinear system. The second presents a case of nonlinear echo cancellation in a telephone line, concluding with the modeling of a binary alcohol distillation column. Additionally, a possible MISO extension and design guidelines for using the column LNet model in a predictive control strategy are considered. Chapter VI concludes with some remarks and recommendations.

Chapter 2

System Approximation

This chapter presents various input-output approximation structures based both on conventional models and on neural networks. For a proper understanding, the concepts involved in the constitution of a neural network are defined: neurons, layers, topologies, etc. A general framework is also defined within which it is possible to specify discrete nonlinear systems that include neural networks. Within this framework, different classes of networks can be identified that allow modeling both dynamic and static systems. Regarding the latter topic, the advantage of using neural networks as universal approximators of nonlinear functions over other types of approximators (polynomials, splines, etc.) is illustrated. The chapter concludes with a summary of what was presented.

2.1 Introduction

Systems theory, which in recent decades has evolved as a scientific discipline of great applicability, deals with the synthesis and analysis of dynamic systems. The best-developed aspects of this theory treat systems defined by linear operators using well-established techniques based on linear algebra, complex variable theory, and the theory of ordinary linear differential equations. The great advances in this area have produced a significant variety of techniques for the analysis and synthesis of linear systems, addressing these problems from different perspectives with respect to the degree of knowledge of the system required. These range from those requiring complete knowledge, through those admitting a certain degree of uncertainty in the system description, to those that identify the system completely. In contrast, and despite the great effort

made in the study of nonlinear systems, most of the work done in this area requires complete knowledge of the models (see [2, Banks], [29, Isidori]). In many cases this knowledge is not available, nor is access to the states describing the system, which then need to be estimated. When systems are of large dimensions, estimating states in nonlinear systems becomes prohibitive. However, in a wide variety of situations it is possible to use models constructed on the basis of measurements from the available inputs and outputs of the system, which naturally leads to identifying nonlinear input-output models.

In past decades, a wide variety of methods have been developed for identifying dynamic nonlinear systems based on input-output data. In most cases (if not all) the identification of such schemes involves determining some type of nonlinear function, such as the kernels in Volterra series. Moreover, most of them assume *a priori* knowledge of the system structure. And even when methods for estimating such structures exist (however complicated they may be), these methods found limited application due to the inherent difficulty of estimating the nonlinear functions involved in their structures. In this sense, the emergence of techniques such as neural networks produced substantial changes.

The application of artificial neural network techniques has produced a vigorous revival and broad expansion in the field of nonlinear systems. Much of this revival is explained by the relative ease with which certain structures, such as the Multilayer Perceptron, can model nonlinear functions in high-dimensional spaces. In this field, wholly novel structures coexist with a significant number arising from modifications of existing approximation schemes. This chapter presents both conventional models and those using neural networks; for proper understanding, the neural network topic is defined in the following section.

2.2 Neural Networks

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) began to be investigated in an attempt to reproduce some of the notable properties of their biological counterparts: feature extraction,¹ cause-effect associations, pattern identification and recognition, etc. Since Minsky's early work in the 1950s, the topic known in the literature as artificial neural

¹**Feature:** a set of traits that distinguish one thing from others.

networks has been constituted as a set of algorithms and heuristics that seeks to emulate some of the tasks that humans perform very naturally. This objective must not be confused with that of mathematically modeling the behavior of biological neurons, which is the subject of other areas of knowledge [73]. Therefore, the similarities that ANNs maintain with biological networks reduce to: imitating some of their qualities and sharing the terminology. According to these analogies, an artificial *neuron* is the minimum information-processing element found in an artificial network. A *network* is then formed by a large number of these simple elements densely interconnected. The way neurons connect with each other defines in general the *topology* of the network and in particular the substructures called *layers*. It should be noted that it is not always possible to define layers in a network topology. A relevant feature of a network is whether or not feedback exists among any of its parts—for example, among neurons, between inputs and outputs, and/or between layers. This property generates a first major division among networks into: those *with feedback or recurrent* and those *without feedback or feedforward*. The latter are generally capable of modeling objects without dynamics (nonlinear function systems), while the former allow modeling dynamic objects (nonlinear differential equation systems). Both types of networks need to adjust their constitutive parameters, and by analogy with what occurs in biological neural networks, an ANN is said to *learn*.

The concept of learning refers to the way in which the algorithms used modify the network parameters in order to achieve a given objective. For example, if one wishes to classify a set of data into several distinct classes and knows to which class each datum belongs, a *supervised* learning mechanism will efficiently accomplish the task. To implement this type of algorithm it is usual to minimize a given performance index between what is desired and the network output. Within this class, the best-known algorithm is undoubtedly Back Error Propagation [58]. However, information about what is expected at the output is not always available. A typical example is having to classify a set of data into several classes without knowing to which class each datum belongs (“clustering”). This task is performed by an *unsupervised* learning algorithm. Within this class, the two most important algorithms are Kohonen’s Self-Organizing Map [30] and Grossberg’s Adaptive Resonance Theory [10]. Figure 2.1 shows a possible classification of networks according to their interconnection scheme and the type of training algorithms.

Figure 2.1: Classification Scheme of Artificial Neural Networks.

As can be inferred, there exists a wide variety of artificial neural networks, many specialized with specific capabilities, just as in their biological counterpart. These models range from the simplest, whose neurons compute some measure of the distance between inputs and weights, to those that integrate, correlate, or perform other even more complex temporal operations on their inputs [34]. Due to the great variety of existing artificial neural network models, only the network model with which we will work will be explicitly described, providing the necessary bibliographic references whenever required. Figure 2.2 shows an artificial neuron with:

u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m : a set of *inputs*.

w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m : a set of *synaptic weights*.

b : the *threshold* value (or “bias”).

ϕ : the *activation function*.

This diagram shows how the flow of signals in our typical neuron can be interpreted. A small black square represents a scalar value that multiplies the signal “flowing” through the solid line (e.g., $u_1 w_1$). Circles with the symbol \sum express the sum of the signals arriving at them (e.g., $w_1 u_1 + w_2 u_2 + \dots + w_m u_m + b$). The square with the symbol ϕ inside represents a static nonlinear transformation that can take various forms: sign function, hyperbolic arctangent function, or in general any function [35]. The threshold

Figure 2.2: Scheme of an Artificial Neuron.

value b will be considered as an additional weight (for simplicity), assuming a utility input that remains constant at a unit value (by convention). This graphical interpretation is convenient for understanding the mathematical definitions of neuron, layer, and network. The output value s of a neuron can therefore be expressed as

$$s = \left| \mathbf{w}^T \begin{matrix} b \\ \mathbf{u} \\ 1 \end{matrix} \right| = w_1 u_1 + w_2 u_2 + \cdots + w_m u_m + b,$$

where $\mathbf{u} = [u_1 \ u_2 \ \dots \ u_m]^T$ is the input vector and $\mathbf{w} = [w_1 \ w_2 \ \dots \ w_m]^T$ the weight vector. For more compact notation, let \mathbf{U} , \mathbf{S} , and \mathbf{Y} be real vector spaces with $\dim(\mathbf{U}) = m$, $\dim(\mathbf{S}) = \dim(\mathbf{Y}) = 1$. Let $\alpha : \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}$ be a real affine transformation of the form

$$s = \alpha(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{u} + b, \quad (2.1)$$

where $b \in S$, $\mathbf{u} = [u_1 \ u_2 \ \dots \ u_m]^T$, $\mathbf{w} = [w_1 \ w_2 \ \dots \ w_m]^T$, $(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}) \in U$, and $\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{u} : \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}$. Let ϕ be an activation function, $\phi : \mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$, such that the output of a neuron can be expressed as

$$y = \phi(\alpha(\mathbf{u})) = \phi(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{u} + b).$$

A layer is defined by a grouping of no neurons that are not permitted to connect with each other. Let S now be a real vector space of finite dimension $\dim(S) = no$, defining the layer order. Note that the dimension of the space S varies according to whether it

refers to a neuron $\dim(S) = 1$ or a layer $\dim(S) = no$. Let $\alpha : \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}$ be an affine transformation such that

$$s = \alpha(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{b},$$

where $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbf{S}$, $\mathbf{W} : [no \times m]$, $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_1 \ \mathbf{w}_2 \ \dots \ \mathbf{w}_{no}]^T$, with $\mathbf{w}_i \in \mathbf{U}$ representing the neuron weight vectors, $\mathbf{W}\mathbf{u} : \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}$. Let ϕ be the layer activation function, $\phi : \mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$, such that

$$\phi(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{no}) = (\phi_1(s_1), \phi_2(s_2), \dots, \phi_{no}(s_{no})), \quad (2.2)$$

where each ϕ_i , $i : 1, 2, \dots, no$ is the activation function of a neuron. We interpret a layer of order no as the realization of a continuous function $\mathbf{y} : \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$ of the form $\mathbf{y} = \phi(\mathbf{W}\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{b})$. This type of topology constitutes what we call *flat layers*. A flat layer is then defined by the set of values $(\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b}, \phi)$, or referring specifically to the i -th layer through an operator of the form

$$\mathbf{N}_i[\mathbf{u}] = \phi[\mathbf{W}_i \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{b}_i]. \quad (2.3)$$

The way in which a grouping of neurons produces a structure called a layer has been illustrated. The following sections will show that a network is composed of a certain number of interconnected layers. The different ways of interconnecting layers give rise to multilayer networks, recurrent networks, or generalized networks. Each category will be illustrated with an example considered typical or highly representative of the class, with corresponding references for other types.

2.2.1 Multilayer Networks

Figure 2.3 shows a typical feedforward (non-recurrent) multilayer network composed of an input layer with m inputs, two hidden layers with no_1 and no_2 neurons respectively, and an output layer with d outputs. In operator form this network can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{N}[\mathbf{u}] = \mathbf{N}_3 \mathbf{N}_2 \mathbf{N}_1[\mathbf{u}] = \phi[\mathbf{W}_3 \phi[\mathbf{W}_2 \phi[\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{b}_1] + \mathbf{b}_2] + \mathbf{b}_3].$$

The addition of more layers does not conceptually add any extra complexity. Figure 2.4 shows a block diagram of the same network. The main characteristic of this type of

network is that they produce at the output a static nonlinear transformation of the input signals. It should be noted that there are other types of multilayer networks such as Radial Basis Networks [47], with the Multilayer Perceptron being a classic example of this class.

Multilayer Perceptron

This is perhaps the best-known neural network and has been the subject of the most varied studies, beginning with Minsky in the 1950s. The Multilayer Perceptron is a type of artificial neural network consisting of nc flat layers as described by equation 2.3. The layers between the output and input are called hidden layers for historical reasons, with each layer having no_i nodes or neurons, $i : 1, \dots, nc$. Figure 2.3 shows such an arrangement of three layers: hidden layers 1 and 2 and the output layer 3. Figure 2.4

Figure 2.3: Multilayer Network Structure.

shows a pictorial diagram in which each layer is represented only by its matrix W_i . A prominent place within this type of networks is occupied by the single hidden layer Perceptron. This neural network constitutes an approximator of continuous functions

Figure 2.4: Pictorial Diagram of a Multilayer Network.

parameterized by the synaptic weights of its no hidden neurons. For the particular case

$y : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$:

$$y = \sum_{k=1}^{no} w2_k \phi(\mathbf{w1}_k^T \mathbf{u} + b1_k) + b2, \quad (2.4)$$

or in its operator form as

$$y = NN(\mathbf{u}). \quad (2.5)$$

Given its relative importance, the following theorem is worth citing.

Theorem 1 (Cybenko, 1989). *Let $C(\mathbf{I}_m)$ be the space of continuous functions defined on the m -dimensional unit cube \mathbf{I}_m . Then, given any $g \in C(\mathbf{I}_m)$, any continuous sigmoid function ϕ , and $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists a finite sum of no terms*

$$g_{no}(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{k=1}^{no} w2_k \phi(\mathbf{w1}_k^T \mathbf{u} + b1_k) + b2,$$

where $\mathbf{w1}_k^T \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $b1_k$, $w2_k$, $b2 \in \mathbb{R}$ are the neural network parameters, such that

$$|g_{no}(\mathbf{u}) - g(\mathbf{u})| < \varepsilon$$

for all $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbf{I}_m$.

The different ways of expressing a single hidden layer Perceptron will be useful in subsequent developments. The following sections present other types of networks: those that incorporate feedback among their parts.

2.2.2 Recurrent Networks

As expressed in previous sections, recurrent networks are distinguished from non-recurrent ones by incorporating some form of feedback in their structure. There exists a wide variety of topologies that feed back signals from other neurons, internal states, and/or outputs. The logical way to represent them is through nonlinear dynamic systems. Among the notable applications using this type of network are nonlinear system identification, nonlinear signal processing, and pattern identification and reconstruction from noisy data. It is precisely in this last application that the appearance of recurrent networks is recognized: the Hopfield network. For a survey of this class of networks see [23] and the references cited therein. Recurrent networks were originally presented in

Hopfield's early work in the field [27]. Since then they have been extensively investigated as an alternative solution to various problems, including the reconstruction of noisy patterns. The discrete version of the Hopfield network, schematized in Figure 2.5, is discussed below. This network can be seen to consist of a single layer of neurons with

Figure 2.5: Representation of the Hopfield Network.

an equal number of inputs and outputs, which are fed back to the input. The feedback is implemented through a set of delay operators q^{-1} . It is easy to see that this network can be described by the following discrete nonlinear system

$$\mathbf{x}(k+1) = \phi[\mathbf{W}\mathbf{x}(k)], \quad \mathbf{x}(0) = \mathbf{x}_0, \quad (2.6)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(k)$ represents the network states at instant k . Another way to represent it is through the flat layer operator $\mathbf{N}_1[\cdot]$:

$$\mathbf{x}(k+1) = \mathbf{N}_1[\mathbf{x}](k), \quad \mathbf{x}(0) = \mathbf{x}_0.$$

Suppose a set of noisy patterns is available and one wishes to filter them to remove the noise. To this end a network such as the one described, previously trained with the noise-free patterns whose information is stored in the matrix \mathbf{W} , is used. The operating mode of this network is very particular, since the noise-free patterns are stored as strange

attractors.² The noisy patterns are then included as the initial state \mathbf{x}_0 of the network. In this way, the dynamic system described by 2.6 evolves until it reaches a new equilibrium point (strange attractor) that turns out to be the desired noise-free pattern. Figure 2.6 shows a schematic diagram of this network. This network has a very complex dynamic

Figure 2.6: Block Diagram Representation of the Hopfield Network.

evolution due to its particular mode of operation. This illustrates one of the most difficult situations in recurrent networks: stability. Stability conditions for the Hopfield network have been established in terms of the matrix \mathbf{W} representing the discrete nonlinear system 2.6. It is worth noting as an interesting fact that a network with very complex dynamics results from the combination of static layers such as 2.3 and simple delay elements such as 1.6. If, instead of simple delay operators, linear dynamic systems are used, this concept can be extended to what will be called generalized networks.

2.2.3 Generalized Networks

The previous section illustrated how, starting from elements such as the layer operator $\mathbf{N}_i[\cdot]$ 2.3 and the unit delay operator $q^{-1}[\cdot]$ 1.6 connected in the feedback, it is possible to construct recurrent networks such as 2.6. These concepts can be generalized [50], giving rise to more complex structures developed from simpler and well-known elements. This is advantageous since it provides a generalized framework for denoting both networks that perform static transformations and networks that, having recurrence, must be modeled as dynamic systems. The generating elements of generalized networks

²*Strange attractor*: a region of state space that attracts nearby orbits of the system without being an equilibrium point, a limit cycle, or a quasi-stationary cycle. Once in the strange attractor region, the orbits remain there.

are:

$\mathbf{N}_i[\cdot]$: layers of static nonlinear transformations.

$\mathbf{G}_i(\cdot)$: matrices of transfer functions.

From the combination of these elements, a wide diversity of different networks arises. Figure 2.7 illustrates four possible generalized structures in which a wide variety of known models are represented. The following section describes various input-output

Figure 2.7: Generalized Network Structures: Various Schemes.

approximation schemes, both those that use neural networks in their structure and conventional ones that do not.

2.3 Various Input-Output Approximation Models

This section presents various input-output approximation schemes, divided for better organization into conventional and non-conventional. Among the former are the functional approximation methods based on Volterra and Wiener series, cascade block models, and cascade-parallel block models. Among the latter, characterized by incorporating neural networks in their structures: Nonlinear FIR and IIR models and an internal approximation scheme for nonlinear systems with fading memory. In all cases, discrete

nonlinear systems as described by 1.20 are considered, with input $u(k)$ and output $\tilde{y}(k)$ approximating the system output $y(k)$, as shown in Figure 2.8.

2.3.1 Conventional Schemes

Functional Expansion Methods

Figure 2.8: Scheme of the System and its Approximating Model.

A functional expansion of a system refers to an input-output representation of the system such as:

$$y(t) = Fun[u(t'); t' \leq t],$$

where $y(t)$ and $u(t)$ are the system output and input at time t , and $Fun[\cdot]$ represents the desired functional. This allows the output value to be evaluated at any time t , given the evolution of the input $u(t')$ for all $t' \leq t$. The implementation of these approximation strategies in the linear case leads to representations such as those shown in equations 1.14 and 1.19. When dealing with functional expansion methods in the context of nonlinear system identification, the natural reference is to Volterra and Wiener series.

Volterra Series Method The study of analytic functionals began in 1887 with Volterra's investigations, who introduced the representation

$$y(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_{\Omega} \cdots \int_{\Omega} k_n(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) \prod_{i=1}^n u(t - \tau_i) d\tau_i, \quad (2.7)$$

widely known as the Volterra series. The functions $k_n(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n)$ in the variables τ_i of equation 2.7 are called Volterra kernels, valid in the domain Ω . For continuous, causal, shift-invariant nonlinear systems, the kernels are bounded, symmetric, and continuous

with respect to each τ_j , with $k_n(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n) = 0$ for any $\tau_j < 0$. The solution of the identification problem based on Volterra series involves measuring the Volterra kernels [1]. It can be observed that series 2.7 is infinite, indicating that it must first be truncated to identify it. The discrete Volterra series is presented below:

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \sum_{m=0}^{mv} \sum_{i_1=0}^{lm-1} \cdots \sum_{i_m=0}^{lm-1} k_m(i_1, \dots, i_m) u(k - i_1) \cdots u(k - i_m). \quad (2.8)$$

In equation 2.8, m is the series order, which has finite memory lm , and k_m is a symmetric kernel of m -th order. This series can uniformly approximate discrete nonlinear systems with finite memory, causal and time-invariant, over a uniformly bounded set of inputs, provided a sufficiently high order m is considered. This is precisely the bottleneck of the Volterra series method, even for kernels of moderate dimension. For measuring the kernels $k_m(\cdot)$, techniques ranging from gradient minimization to frequency-domain measurements and higher-order correlations have been used [4]. The difficulties in estimating these kernels have restricted applications to expansions with kernels of dimension ≤ 2 [4, 43]. Volterra's work was taken up and continued by Wiener in the 1950s.

Wiener Series Method Wiener was one of the first authors to consider the identification of nonlinear systems. Consider a causal, time-invariant continuous nonlinear system with $y(t)$ the output and $u(t)$ the input at time t . The functional used by Wiener to expand the system can be expressed as

$$y(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m_0=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m_1=0}^{\infty} \cdots \sum_{m_n=0}^{\infty} c_{m_0 m_1 \dots m_n} ph_{m_0}(vv_0(t)) ph_{m_0_1}(vv_1(t)) \cdots ph_{m_n}(vv_n(t)), \quad (2.9)$$

where $c_{m_0 m_1 \dots m_n}$ represents the expansion coefficients, $vv_p(t)$ are auxiliary variables combined by the Hermite polynomials $ph_{m_n}(\cdot)$. The auxiliary variables $vv_p(t)$ represent the convolution of the input signal $u(t)$ with the Laguerre system $l_p(t)$ of order

$$vv_p(t) = \int_0^{\infty} l_p(\tau) u(t - \tau) d\tau, \quad p = 0, 1, \dots$$

The partially normalized Hermite polynomial $ph_{m_n}(\cdot)$ is defined by

$$ph_{m_n}(u) = (-1)^{m_n} 2^{-m_n/2} \frac{e^{u^2}}{\sqrt{m_n!}} \frac{d^{m_n}}{du^{m_n}} \left\{ e^{-u^2} \right\}.$$

The synthesis of a nonlinear system using the Wiener method can be visualized as a cascade of three distinct blocks, as shown in Figure 2.9. The first is a linear multi-output system composed of Laguerre systems. This is followed in cascade by a memoryless nonlinear transformation representing the Hermite polynomials. Culminating with a network of amplifiers and adders: the coefficients $c_{m_0 m_1 \dots m_n}$ of the expansion.

Figure 2.9: Wiener Method

Although the Wiener formulation is theoretically very elegant, it is impractical and difficult to apply due to the large number of required coefficients. If n Laguerre systems and Hermite polynomials of order m_n are used, $(m_n)^n$ coefficients are needed to characterize the system. Thus even for a system composed of a second-order nonlinearity using 10 Laguerre systems, on the order of 2^{10} coefficients would be required. This is why most practical applications have been restricted to quadratic systems [4], although theoretical results exist showing fundamental difficulties for the evaluation of kernels of order ≥ 3 [54]. Unlike what happens with Volterra series, the discrete versions of these series have been used in only a few cases [32].

Wiener and Volterra series expansions have been limited to realizations where the kernel order is low, due to the large number of associated parameters that must be identified. Cascade block systems arise as an attempt to solve the identification problem by seeking more compact representations in terms of number of parameters.

Identification of Cascade Block Models

Cascade block systems began to be studied by various authors in a search to reduce the high computational burden associated with functional series approximations. Figure 2.10 schematizes these models through the interconnection of linear dynamic systems and static nonlinear elements, as can be seen in [32]. The scheme consists of two

Figure 2.10: General Cascade Model.

linear dynamic systems represented by the impulse responses $hgc_1(k)$ and $hgc_2(k)$ and a memoryless nonlinear system represented by $ff(\cdot)$. The system is approximated from an input-output perspective, taking into account that the signals $t(k)$ and $s(k)$ are not accessible for measurement. As a direct consequence, the methods for estimating $hgc_1(k)$ and $hgc_2(k)$ have been varied. However, all these techniques share the requirement of long experimentation and data acquisition times, which can be prohibitive in many cases. A simpler method for solving the identification problem was developed by Korenberg [32], using correlation techniques and Fourier transforms to identify $hgc_1(k)$ and $hgc_2(k)$. Once these impulse responses are estimated, the values of signals $t(k)$ and $s(k)$ can be evaluated and the function $ff(\cdot)$ plotted. The disadvantages of this method are:

1. It is a graphical method (the function $ff(\cdot)$ must be plotted).
2. Depending on whether this function is even or odd, higher-order correlations must be computed to completely identify the model.

As a way to simplify the involved calculations, other widely used models appeared that constitute sub-structures of the general model. The well-known cases of the Wiener model, with $hgc_2(k) = \delta(k)$,³ and the Hammerstein model [49] with $hgc_1(k) = \delta(k)$ can be cited. It has been seen that cascade block methods have an advantage over functional expansion methods in terms of the number of terms required. However, being graphical methods, they have not been widely used. The cascade-parallel block methods constitute an improvement with respect to both aspects.

³ $\delta(k)$: represents the unit impulse.

Parallel Cascade Block Models

This method developed by Korenberg [33] consists of the parallel connection of several sections composed of the cascade of a linear dynamic system and a static nonlinearity, as shown in Figure 2.11. The implicit approximation philosophy can be

Figure 2.11: Cascade/Parallel Section Method.

thought of as combining those of the functional expansion methods and cascade block models. On one hand, cascades of linear dynamic systems and static nonlinearities are used, similar to cascade block systems. On the other hand, parallel branches of block cascades (as in functional series) are progressively added until the desired approximation is gradually achieved. The essence of the method consists of approximating the output of the nonlinear system by a first cascade of a linear system with a static nonlinearity. The residual between this first cascade's output and the nonlinear system is then computed, and this residual is fitted by a second cascade. Continuing this process, the algorithm converges in the mean-square sense [33]. This method is applicable to any discrete, time-invariant, causal nonlinear system. Mathematically this can be expressed as:

$$y(k) = \sum_{i=1}^I v_i(k) + e(k),$$

where $v_i(k)$ is the output of the i -th cascade and $y(k)$ the system output as usual. The linear subsystem of the i -th cascade is characterized by its impulse response $h_{cp_i}(m)$, with memory length $lm = r$, while the nonlinearity is characterized by the polynomial $p_i(\cdot)$. Assuming it has been computed up to section $i - 1$ and given np data:

1. Compute $\tilde{y}_{i-1}(k)$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, np$, the remaining residual $\left(\tilde{y}(k) - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_j(k)\right)$ after the $(i-1)$ -th iteration, where $\tilde{y}_0(k) = y(k)$
2. **IF** the residual $\tilde{y}_{i-1}(k)$ is sufficiently small, **STOP**; otherwise, approximate $\tilde{y}_{i-1}(k)$ with the i -th cascade.
3. The impulse response $hcp_i(m)$, $m = 0, 1, \dots, r$ is selected randomly from two correlations, namely: the first

$$hcp_i(k) = \sum_{k=r}^{k=np} \tilde{y}_{i-1}(k) u(k-m),$$

or the higher-order correlation

$$hcp_i(m) = \sum_{k=r}^{k=np} u(k-a) u(k-m) \tilde{y}_{i-1}(k) \pm kk \delta(m-k),$$

where:

- the sign of the term $\delta(m-k)$ is chosen randomly.
- the constant a is selected randomly from $\{0, 1, \dots, r\}$.
- the term kk tends to zero as the mean square of the residuals tends to zero:

$$kk = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{np} \tilde{y}_{i-1}^2(k)}{\sum_{k=0}^{np} \tilde{y}_0^2(k)}.$$

4. Compute $t_i(k) = \sum_{m=1}^r hcp_i(k) u(k-m)$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, np$.
5. Compute the polynomial $p_i(\cdot)$ with input t_i that best fits \tilde{y}_{i-1} on $[0, 1, \dots, np]$, determining the cascade nonlinearity. Then evaluate the output v_i , set $i = i + 1$, and return to step **1**.

With this last case the conventional methods are concluded, and the non-conventional schemes are now described.

2.3.2 Non-Conventional Schemes

This section includes some of the models that use networks for system identification. Two widely used models that will be illustrated are the Nonlinear FIR and

IIR cases, in which the nonlinearities are single hidden layer Perceptrons. Additionally, a case of internal structure approximation of a discrete nonlinear system with fading memory is presented, given the particular nature of the resulting structure.

Delayed-Value Networks

This is the case known as the Nonlinear FIR, which in the generalized network framework corresponds to Figure 2.7b. For this model, Boyd and Chua [6] proved that any discrete, time-invariant, fading-memory nonlinear operator can be approximated by a delay line followed by a memoryless nonlinear transformation, i.e., a polynomial. Sandberg [60] proved that any discrete, time-invariant nonlinear system with approximately finite memory can be uniformly approximated by a delay line followed by a single hidden layer Perceptron. Using different considerations, Matthews [42] developed the same type of structure under different assumptions. Consider the model with a single input, single output, and memory length n_u . Then $\mathbf{G}(q^{-1}) = R^{n_u}(\cdot)$, where $R^{n_u}(\cdot)$ is expressed by 1.7, $\mathbf{N}_2 = \mathbf{I}$ is the identity operator, and a Perceptron with no hidden neurons:

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{no} w_{2i} \phi(\mathbf{w}_1^T \mathbf{u}_{nu}(k) + b_{1i}) + b_2,$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{nu}(k)$ is expressed by 1.8. This can also be expressed as

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \mathbf{w}_2 \phi[\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{b}_1] + b_2. \quad (2.10)$$

This approximation scheme, although conceptually intuitive, is difficult to implement when estimating the network parameters, particularly when the system memory n_u is large. The following presents the equivalent case of an ARMAX filter where input and output regressors are related by a single hidden layer Perceptron.

NARMAX Models with Networks

This type of model, presented by Narendra et al. [50], consists simply of input and output delay lines as in a common ARMAX filter, but nonlinearly related by a single hidden layer Perceptron. This model corresponds to the structure of Figure 2.7c. Assuming input regressors of order nu , output regressors of order ny , and a Perceptron

with *no* hidden neurons: $\mathbf{G}_1(q^{-1}) = R^{nu}(\cdot)$, $\mathbf{G}_2(q^{-1}) = R^{ny}(\cdot)$,

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{no} w2_i \phi \left(\mathbf{w1}^T \left[\mathbf{u}_{nu}(k)^T \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}(k)^T \right]^T + b1_i \right) + b2,$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{nu}(k)$ is expressed by 1.8 and $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny}$ by 1.11. This can also be expressed as

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \mathbf{w2} \phi \left[\mathbf{W1} \left[\mathbf{u}_{nu} \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{ny} \right] + \mathbf{bi} \right] + b2.$$

This structure, while concise in terms of the description achieved, retains stability problems in its adjustment due to the feedback present [50]. The next section shows a model of the internal representation of fading-memory systems.

Internal Representation of Fading-Memory Schemes

The approximation scheme illustrated below differs from the philosophy of the input-output schemes presented in this section; however, it is included because of the simple form its structure takes. To approximate the internal representation of a discrete, shift-invariant nonlinear system with fading memory, the following representation is sufficient:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(k+1) &= \phi \left[\mathbf{Ax}(k) + \mathbf{Bu}(k) \right] & k \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \\ \mathbf{y}(k) &= \mathbf{Cx}(k) \end{aligned}, \quad (2.11)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(k) = [x_1(k), x_2(k), \dots, x_n(k)]$ represents the n states; $\mathbf{u}(k) = [u_1(k), u_2(k), \dots, u_p(k)]$, the p inputs and $\mathbf{y}(k) = [y_1(k), y_2(k), \dots, y_m(k)]$ the m outputs. The structure matrices are $\mathbf{A} : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$, $\mathbf{B} : \mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, and $\mathbf{C} : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$. This scheme can be expressed within the generalized network framework, coinciding with the scheme of Figure 2.7d, for $\mathbf{N}_1[\cdot] = \phi$, $\mathbf{N}_2[\cdot] = \mathbf{B}$, $\mathbf{N}_3[\cdot] = \mathbf{A}$, $\mathbf{N}_4[\cdot] = \mathbf{C}$, $\mathbf{G}(q^{-1}) = q^{-1}\mathbf{I}$. However, beyond the simple resulting approximation structure, this model retains the difficulties found in recurrent networks: difficulty in ensuring stability and training algorithms that are hard to implement. In [42] a recursive algorithm is proposed to estimate the parameters of 2.11, proving that if the eigenvalues of matrix \mathbf{A} are less than 1 ($\text{eig}(\mathbf{A}) < 1$) the system is stable. However, the inconvenience of having to compute the eigenvalues of a matrix for a recursive estimation algorithm is well known, imposing a severe constraint on the calculations involved.

Various cases of approximation schemes using networks and conventional-type schemes have been presented. The following section treats the case of the LNet structure.

2.4 The LNet Structure

This section illustrates the advantages of using a single hidden layer Perceptron in the LNet structure instead of other approximators such as polynomials. The class of models that use polynomials in their structures is known in the literature as *polynomial filters* [43, 26], with the Wiener series model 2.9 being a typical example. Figure 2.9 shows the scheme of a Wiener series method realization for continuous nonlinear systems. As mentioned in previous sections, certain approximation structures using networks arise from modifying pre-existing models. Figure 2.12 shows the LNet structure scheme, where it can be seen that there is a set of Laguerre systems just as in Figure 2.9. However, the two structures differ in the way these systems are nonlinearly related. In the Wiener structure of Figure 2.9 this relationship is carried out by a set of Hermite polynomials. Figure 2.12 represents the nonlinear combination of m Laguerre

Figure 2.12: LNet Structure

systems 1.15 by a Perceptron with no neurons in its single hidden layer. The output $\tilde{y}(k)$ is

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{no} w2_i \phi(\mathbf{w}1_i^T \mathbf{u}_L(k) + b_i) + b2,$$

where $\mathbf{u}_L(k)$ is indicated by 1.32. An alternative, more compact way of expressing this equation is

$$\tilde{y}(k) = \mathbf{w}2\phi(\mathbf{W}\mathbf{1}^T\mathbf{u}_L(k) + \mathbf{b}) + b2.$$

The single hidden layer Perceptron is the characteristic element of the LNet structure. Its use is justified by several advantages that the developed structure has over polynomial filters. The LNet structure outperforms polynomial filters in aspects related to stability, the number of terms needed to achieve a given approximation, and generalization capability. These factors are detailed below.

Enunciado 1. *Suppose one wishes to approximate a given function $g : \mathcal{C}(\mathbf{U}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on the compact domain $\mathbf{U} \subset \mathbb{R}^m$ by g_n , a homogeneous polynomial of order n , and by g_{no} , a single hidden layer Perceptron with no neurons. With the neural network g_{no} an integral approximation error of $O(1/no)$ is obtained using $O(m \cdot no)$ parameters. With the polynomial g_n an integral approximation error of $O(1/n^{2/m})$ is obtained using $O(n^m)$ parameters. This demonstrates the advantage of approximating functions with networks when the dimension of the space \mathbf{U} is $m \geq 3$.*

This was proved by Barron [3] for functions $g \in C(\mathbf{U})$, $g : \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where $C(\mathbf{U})$ is the space of continuous functions taking values in the compact domain $\mathbf{U} \subset \mathbb{R}^m$, satisfying certain smoothness conditions. Concretely, we are interested in approximating such functions g by polynomials g_n of order n and by g_{no} a single hidden layer Perceptron with no neurons. To facilitate comparison, we use notation that allows expressing both polynomials and networks jointly. Let $g_a : \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be approximators of the form

$$g_a(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{i=0}^{nt} a_i \Psi_i(\mathbf{u}), \quad (2.12)$$

where both $\Psi_i(\cdot)$, the basis functions with which the approximation is performed, and n_t depend on the type of approximator being used. For polynomials, the subscript i is associated with a multi-index $[i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m]$ expressing the powers involved, in the

following form

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 i & [i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{m-1}, i_m] \\
 0 & [0, 0, \dots, 0, 0] \\
 1 & [1, 0, \dots, 0, 0] \\
 2 & [0, 1, \dots, 0, 0] \\
 \vdots & \vdots \\
 nt - 1 & [0, 0, \dots, n, 0] \\
 nt & [0, 0, \dots, 0, n]
 \end{array}$$

with the usual restriction $i_1 + i_2 + \dots + i_m \leq n$. Given the input $\mathbf{u} = [u_1 u_2 \dots u_m]^T$ and based on the multi-index $[i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m]$, the basis functions take the form

$$\Psi_i(\mathbf{u}) = (u_1)^{i_1} (u_2)^{i_2} \dots (u_m)^{i_m}, \quad (2.13)$$

where $(u_j)^{i_s}$ defines the j -th component of the input raised to the i_s -th power. Thus $\Psi_0(\mathbf{u}) = 1$, $\Psi_1(\mathbf{u}) = u_1$, \dots , $\Psi_{nt}(\mathbf{u}) = (u_m)^{i_s}$, so that homogeneous polynomials g_n of order n can be expressed as

$$g_n(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{i=0}^{nt} a_i \Psi_i(\mathbf{u}),$$

where $a_i \in \mathbb{R}$ are the polynomial coefficients and

$$nt = \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{m-i+1}{i}. \quad (2.14)$$

Equation 2.14, where $\binom{\cdot}{\cdot}$ represents the combinatorial operation, shows the exponential variation in the number of terms in a polynomial with respect to the order n and dimension m .

For single hidden layer Perceptrons, the basis functions take the form

$$\Psi_i(\mathbf{u}) = \phi(\mathbf{w}\mathbf{1}_i^T \mathbf{u} + b_i), \quad (2.15)$$

where $\mathbf{w}\mathbf{1}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $b_k \in \mathbb{R}$ with activation function $\phi(s)$ such that $\phi(s) \rightarrow 1$ when $s \rightarrow \infty$

and $\phi(s) \rightarrow 0$ when $s \rightarrow -\infty$. The approximator in this case can be expressed as

$$g_{no}(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{i=0}^{no} w2_i \Psi_i(\mathbf{u}),$$

where $w2_k \in \mathbb{R}$ are the output layer weights.

The functions $g: \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ must also satisfy certain smoothness conditions defined through their Fourier transform:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} g(\mathbf{u}) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^m} e^{j\omega^T \mathbf{u}} \tilde{g}(\omega) d\omega \\ \tilde{g}(\omega) &= (2\pi)^{-m} \int_{\mathbb{R}^m} e^{-j\omega^T \mathbf{u}} g(\mathbf{u}) d\mathbf{u} \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (2.16)$$

where the complex function $\tilde{g}(\omega)$ is the transform of g , with $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_m)$ the frequency vector. The smoothness condition of g is characterized by the property:

$$C_g = \int_{\mathbb{R}^m} \|\omega\| |\tilde{g}(\omega)| d\omega < \infty, \quad (2.17)$$

where $\|\omega\| = (\omega^T \omega)^{1/2}$. Suppose the compact space \mathbf{U} is chosen as the ball $\mathbf{B}_r = \{\mathbf{u} : \|\mathbf{u}\| \leq r, r > 0\}$. Condition 2.17 imposing that C_g be finite implies the integrability of the gradient of g . We denote by $\Gamma_{\mathbf{B}_r}$ the set of functions g with an integrable gradient and a continuous extension of the gradient from \mathbf{B}_r to \mathbb{R}^m . The following theorem then holds.

Theorem 2 (Barron, 1993). *For each function g in $\Gamma_{\mathbf{B}_r}$, each sigmoid function ϕ , each probability measure μ , and each $no \geq 1$, there exists a linear combination of sigmoid functions $g_{no}(\mathbf{u})$ of the form shown in 2.4, such that*

$$\int_{\mathbf{B}_r} (g(\mathbf{u}) - g_{no}(\mathbf{u}))^2 \mu(d\mathbf{u}) \leq \frac{(2rC_g)^2}{no}.$$

If the Lebesgue measure⁴ is used as the probability measure μ , the surprising

⁴Of measurable functions only this simple definition needs to be known, as the topic deserves a treatise in itself.

Definición 1 (Measurable Function:). *We say that a function $f: R_+ \rightarrow R$ is measurable if and only if $f(u)$ is the limit of a step function or piecewise-constant function for all u except those belonging to a set of measure zero ([74, p. 271]).*

result is obtained that the approximation rate achieved is independent of the dimension m , using $O(m \cdot no)$ parameters, which grows only linearly with m . This contrasts with the exponential $O(n^m)$ number of parameters required by methods such as traditional polynomials (see equation 2.14), splines, and series expansions to achieve an approximation rate no better than $O(1/n^{2/m})$ (see [3]). *The factor $(\cdot)^{2/m}$, which acts as the “curse of dimensionality” in polynomials, is absent in networks.* Only if a high degree of smoothness is assumed in the involved functions, i.e., if $\int \|\omega\|^m |g(\omega)|^2 d\omega < \infty$, can the same approximation order as networks be achieved by these approximators, but at the cost of using $O(n^m)$ parameters. This shows a great advantage of network approximation due to their great economy of terms used for dimensions $m \geq 3$, as demonstrated by the previous theorem. A more common situation in the problem of approximating functions is one in which only np values of $g(\cdot)$ are known—i.e., the values $g(\mathbf{u}_i)$ for $\mathbf{u}_i \in B_r$, $i : 1, \dots, np$ are available. In this case the previous theorem specifies the following bound

$$\frac{1}{np} \sum_{i=1}^{np} (g(\mathbf{u}_i) - g_{no}(\mathbf{u}_i))^2 \leq \frac{(2rC_g)^2}{no}, \quad (2.18)$$

for the approximation error [3]. A reasonable explanation for this behavior is that networks can adapt the basis functions used in the approximation to the characteristics of the function being approximated. The following example aims to clarify this point.

Example 2. *It is easy to see that the functions $\Psi_i(\mathbf{u})$ of equation 2.15 can adapt to the shape of the function being approximated by varying the parameters $\mathbf{w}\mathbf{1}_k$ and b_k . This behavior differs from that found in polynomials, where these basis functions are taken from a fixed set. Let polynomials in \mathbb{R} of order n , for which the basis function set of equation 2.13 consists of*

$$\{\Psi_i(u)\}_{i=0}^n = \{1, u, u^2, \dots, u^n\}.$$

It is easy to see that for these functions it is not possible to change their form. If instead a single hidden layer Perceptron with no neurons is considered, the basis function set according to equation 2.15 would be

$$\{\Psi_i(u)\}_{i=0}^{no-1} = \{\phi(w_1 u + b_0), \phi(w_2 u + b_1), \dots, \phi(w_{no-1} u + b_{no-1})\},$$

where $\phi(\cdot)$ is a sigmoid. Figure 2.13 illustrates how it is possible to vary the shape of the functions Ψ_i by adjusting the parameters w_{1i} , b_i . It is perhaps the ability to adjust their shape with respect to the function to be approximated that provides such flexibility to networks. ■

Figure 2.13: Sigmoid for Various Parameters: a) $b = cte$. b) $w_1 = cte$.

It should be noted that the effect of dimension can be reflected indirectly through the constant C_g , since this involves an integral in m dimensions. In these cases a relationship is obtained in which dimension m intervenes exponentially through the integral. Comparatively, for this same case the number of terms for a polynomial would be much larger: superexponential. This effect, which in a neural network can be remedied by adding an extra hidden layer, cannot be attenuated in a polynomial. In [24] it is shown that certain problems requiring an exponential number of terms for a single hidden layer network can be solved by a two hidden layer network with a polynomial number of terms. However this topic, while widely known experimentally, still requires a rigorous proof; it remains completely unclear when it is advantageous to use a network with one, two, or more hidden layers.

Enunciado 2. *When polynomials are used to approximate a function, numerical stability*

is difficult to handle even for spaces of moderate dimensions. Additionally, polynomials exhibit pathological behavior in the sense that if a signal is outside the compact set where the approximation is defined, it can be excessively amplified.

Suppose one wishes to fit a function $g : \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on the compact $\mathbf{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$ by a polynomial of order 10. It is easy to see that even for this 3-dimensional space, approximately 3^{10} coefficients would be needed, so the data matrix required for the fit is normally ill-conditioned. This produces serious effects on the stability of the numerical methods used for computing the coefficients.

The characteristic of polynomial filters is precisely the use of a polynomial. Beyond the excessive number of parameters required to achieve a good approximation of a fading-memory system, in a polynomial filter the output grows without limit for inputs outside the compact set \mathbf{U} where the approximation is defined. In most natural systems, some saturation mechanism exists whereby above a certain input level, the outputs do not change in value. This behavior, which is present in network-based approximators since the activation functions produce saturation beyond a certain level of the inputs, is absent in polynomial filters. In other words, input signals outside \mathbf{U} (also called the generalization domain) are amplified excessively by the polynomial filter and must be clipped either at the input or at the output [42]. In [26] an application is presented where the stability problem is highlighted, and a solution is provided by using a sigmoid at the output of the polynomial model, making it more similar to a network than a polynomial. The algebraic properties of polynomial systems were studied by Sontag [70]. Unfortunately, polynomial models are not inherently stable and no general stability criterion exists for such filters. Ensuring stability is essential for the implementation of online parameter estimation algorithms.

Enunciado 3. *In polynomials it is more difficult to deal with the phenomenon of parameter overfitting, unlike what occurs in networks for which certain mechanisms exist to mitigate this undesired effect.*

Consider the case of estimating from samples a continuous function $y = g(\mathbf{u})$, $g : \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ taking values in the compact domain $\mathbf{U} \subset \mathbb{R}^m$. Two disjoint sets of data pairs α and β with realizations in \mathbf{U} are available, namely

$$\alpha : \{(\mathbf{u}_i, y_i) \mid \mathbf{u}_i \in \mathbf{U}, y_i = g(\mathbf{u}_i), i : 1, \dots, n1\}, \quad (2.19)$$

called the training set, and

$$\beta : \{(\mathbf{u}_i, y_i) \mid \mathbf{u}_i \in \mathbf{U}, y_i = g(\mathbf{u}_i), i : 1, \dots, n_2\}, \quad (2.20)$$

called the test set. In the typical function estimation case, the set α is used to fit the estimator's parameters and the set β is used to verify the estimator's generalization. The phenomenon of overfitting manifests itself when the obtained model accurately reproduces the training set α but performs very poorly on the test set β . Figure 2.14 shows a continuous function represented by curve **c**, for which a set of data points (black dots) is available for approximation, and two different estimates represented by curves **a** and **b**. Curve **a** passes exactly through the data, showing oscillatory behavior elsewhere in the domain: it *interpolates* the data, clearly exhibiting overfitting. In contrast, curve **b** is smoother and, without passing exactly through the points, *approximates* the entire curve. As will be shown in the course of this thesis, several mechanisms exist for avoiding

Figure 2.14: Interpolation and Approximation.

parameter overfitting in networks that are not available for polynomials.

2.5 Conclusions

This chapter has presented various input-output approximation structures based both on conventional models and on neural networks. The concepts of neuron, layer, and topology were defined, together with a general framework for specifying discrete nonlinear systems that include neural networks. The advantage of using neural networks as universal approximators of nonlinear functions over other types of approximators such

as polynomials was illustrated. The next chapter addresses theoretical topics concerning the approximation capabilities of the proposed structure.

Chapter 3

LNet: A Structure for Approximating Discrete Nonlinear Systems

In this chapter it is proved that the LNet structure is capable of approximating nonlinear, discrete, time-invariant operators possessing fading memory. A system can be regarded as an operator that transforms an input sequence into an output sequence, so that the approximated operator is the one that represents the input-output behavior of the system.

The development of this chapter begins with the necessary definitions, followed by a brief discussion of operators and functionals that allows the concept of fading memory to be assimilated. It continues with the presentation of the LNet structure approximation theorem, which is proved using a variation of the Stone-Weierstrass Theorem together with three additional lemmas. Following the proof of the theorem establishing the approximation capabilities of the LNet structure, the chapter concludes with a discussion of the results and a summary.

3.1 Introduction

This section establishes the concepts necessary to state the approximation capabilities of the LNet structure shown in Figure 2.12. This structure allows approximating the external representation of a system characterized by an input-output operator. In doing so, it is possible to approximate discrete, time-invariant, nonlinear operators possessing fading memory. The proof of the results obtained makes use of the concept of

fading memory. Formally introduced by Boyd and Chua [6], this concept has been applied in various fields for different purposes. For instance, in [66] a modified version of the small-gain theorem and the concept of asymptotic gain of fading-memory systems are used to establish necessary and sufficient invertibility conditions for certain feedback operators. Starting from similar premises, in [67] robust stability conditions are established for linear and nonlinear feedback systems with fading memory. In connection with neural networks, the concept allows the development of recursive identification algorithms for the internal and external representations of nonlinear systems, as in [42]. In [16], a special class of inputs is characterized and defined that allows minimizing the worst-case approximation error in the identification of fading-memory systems. Related to the identification of linear time-varying systems with fading memory, in [56] several propositions on norm, pointwise, and asymptotic convergence of the involved operators are proved. It will be shown that the concept of fading memory can be assimilated to a modification of the continuity concept of the operator to be approximated. The result is that if an operator has fading memory, this implies continuity of said operator. However, continuity of an operator does not imply that the operator has fading memory. as fading memory, which will be illustrated by the example of a peak-holding operator. To be more precise, some additional definitions and notation are required.

3.1.1 Notation, Definitions and Preliminary Remarks

The set \mathbb{Z} denotes the integers, distinguished between positive integers \mathbb{Z}_+ and non-positive integers \mathbb{Z}_- including 0. The working space is l^∞ , which represents the space of bounded sequences, i.e., functions $\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, equipped with the supremum norm:

$$\|u\|_\infty \triangleq \sup_k |u(k)|.$$

Hence an element $u \in l^\infty$ is a sequence of real numbers such that $|u(k)| < m_1$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $m_1 > 0$. The notion of time in the sequence will be expressed in a slightly different form from the usual one, which allows certain concepts to be formulated more easily. Thus, a sequence u taking values for $k < 0$ represents past events, while $k > 0$ represents future events, with the present logically expressed by the element $u(0)$, as shown in the following table.

<i>Past</i>	<i>Present</i>	<i>Future</i>
negative integers	0	positive integers

The space $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$ represents the restriction of l^∞ to non-positive integer values. Thus a sequence $u \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$ represents: from events occurring in the remote past (as $k \rightarrow -\infty$) to what happens in the present ($k = 0$). Without containing information about future events ($k > 0$). Next we define two functions, relevant to the exposition, that use sequences as operands: functionals and operators.

Definición 2 (*Functional*). A functional is any function $F : l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that maps a causal sequence to a real number.

Definición 3 (*Operator*). An operator is any mapping $N : l^\infty \rightarrow l^\infty$ that transforms one sequence in l^∞ into another sequence in l^∞ .

Brackets in the arguments of functionals and operators will generally be omitted whenever the meaning is clear from context, writing Fu instead of $F[u]$ (a number) and $Nu(k)$ instead of $N[u](k)$ (a sequence at time k). It is easy to see that a system can be represented by an operator, in the form indicated by the following definition.

Definición 4 (*System*). A system is mathematically defined by a function or operator N that transforms an input sequence u into an output sequence y [53]. This fact, schematically represented in Figure 1.1, will be denoted $y(k) = N[u](k)$.

We are interested in the capability of the LNet structure to approximate operators $N : l^\infty \rightarrow l^\infty$, that are nonlinear, time-invariant, and causal. Such operators represent the input-output behavior of the system, transforming bounded input sequences into bounded output sequences (BIBO¹ stable systems). These concepts will be clarified by providing the corresponding definitions, which can be found in [53].

Definición 5 (*Time Invariance*). An operator N that transforms the sequence $u(k)$ into $y(k)$ is said to be shift-invariant if, for all integers τ , $y(k - \tau)$ equals the transformation of $u(k - \tau)$. When the index k refers to time, we speak of time-invariance. Consequently, an operator is time-invariant if $q^\tau N = Nq^\tau$ for all $\tau \in \mathbb{Z}$, where q^τ is the delay operator defined by equation 1.6.

¹BIBO: Bounded-Input-Bounded-Output.

Definición 6 (*Causality*). In a causal system, the output at any time instant $k = k_o$ depends only on the evolution of the input for all time $k \leq k_o$. In colloquial terms, this means that the present does not depend on the future. We say that operator N is causal if $u(k) = v(k)$, $k \leq k_o$, implies $Nu(k) = Nv(k)$ for $k \leq k_o$.

Definición 7 (*Causal Sequence*). Extending the idea of causality to sequences, we say that a sequence u is causal if it takes values only for $k \leq 0$, i.e., if $u \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$.

The previous definition expresses that a causal sequence takes no values for $k > 0$. Since we are interested in operators $N : l^\infty \rightarrow l^\infty$, it is necessary to define a non-causal extension of a causal sequence. One way to do this is to set all future values of the sequence equal to the current value. Proceeding in this way, for every causal sequence $u \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$ we define a continuous non-causal extension $u_e \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z})$ as

$$u_e(k) = \begin{cases} u(k), & k \leq 0 \\ u(0), & k > 0 \end{cases}. \quad (3.1)$$

The inverse path, converting a non-causal sequence into a causal one, is achieved via the truncation operator $P : l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$, which truncates an element $u \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z})$ to an element of $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$ in the following way:

$$Pu(k) \triangleq \begin{cases} u(k), & \text{for } k \leq 0 \\ 0, & \text{for } k > 0 \end{cases}.$$

Figure 3.1a shows a causal sequence with its corresponding non-causal extension in part (b), while part (c) illustrates how the original causal sequence can be recovered through the truncation operator P .

We have seen how an operator N can represent the input-output behavior of a system. If in addition the operator N is time-invariant, it is possible to associate with it a functional F in $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$ (as in [6]) defined as

$$Fu \triangleq Nu_e(0), \quad (3.2)$$

where u_e is the non-causal extension of u from equation 3.1. It is easy to see that $Nu_e(0)$ represents the current output value of the system, which is 0 by convention. This allows the functional F to be interpreted as transforming the *past of the input* u into the present

Figure 3.1: Causal Sequence and use of the Truncation Operator.

output of the system. From this perspective, operator N can be viewed as a functional that transforms the past of the input into the current output for each possible time instant. This establishes the possibility of recovering operator N from its associated functional F , using the relation

$$Nu(k) = FPq^k u, \quad (3.3)$$

through which the operator N is recovered as the variable k takes different values. We next present an example using a linear system to clarify these concepts, where Figure 3.2 illustrates the sequence extension procedure and Figure 3.3 illustrates the procedure for recovering an operator from its associated functional.

Example 3. Figure 3.2 illustrates: in (a), the input sequence $u(k)$; in (b), the sequence $u_e(k)$, the non-causal extension of $u(k)$; in (c), $Nu(k)$, the system response to input $u(k)$; and in (d), $Nu_e(k)$, the response to input $u_e(k)$. The value of Fu is shown highlighted in panel (d).

In Figure 3.3 we see how the operator N can be recovered from the value of the functional F , illustrated for the case $k = -1$ in equation 3.3. Part (a) shows the signal $u(k)$ shifted by q^{-1} , the sequence upon which the truncation operator P acts to generate the sequence $Pq^{-1}u(k)$ shown in part (b). The non-causal version $(Pq^{-1}u)_e(k)$ of the previous sequence is shown in part (c), while part (d) shows the value of the desired functional $FPq^{-1}u$ (highlighted value). This process is illustrated for the value $k = -1$. The operator N is recovered from its functional F by repeating this procedure for each k .

Figure 3.2: Causal, Extended Sequences and Associated Responses.

■

We have seen how an operator represents a system, have defined its properties, and expressed how to associate a functional with each operator and how to recover the operator from its associated functional. Based on the previous definitions and discussions, it is possible to express in compact form the notion of continuity and causality for a time-invariant operator:

Definición 8. *A time-invariant operator N is causal and continuous if and only if for each $u, v \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z})$ and each $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $\delta > 0$ such that*

$$\sup_{k \leq 0} |u(k) - v(k)| < \delta \Rightarrow |Nu(0) - Nv(0)| < \varepsilon. \quad (3.4)$$

This definition expresses that for a continuous operator, the current system output $Nu(0)$ depends continuously on the entire prior history of the input. That is, an event that occurred in the remote past ($k \rightarrow -\infty$) affects the current output in the same way as an event in the recent past (k close to 0). A bistable circuit is a classic example of such a system: to know the current output, the entire input sequence and the initial state must be known. However, the ultimate goal of any theory is to explain reality, and for a large number of real systems the influence of the past of the inputs on the present output diminishes as one goes further back in time. When this concept is incorporated,

Figure 3.3: Reconstruction of Operator N from its Associated Functional F .

one arrives naturally at the class of systems with fading memory.

3.2 Fading Memory

Intuitively, an operator has fading memory if two input signals that are close in some sense in the recent past (but not necessarily in their remote past) produce outputs that are close in the present. The concept of fading memory expresses that as one goes further into the past ($k \rightarrow -\infty$), the influence of the input $u(k)$ on the present output $Nu(0)$ becomes negligible or fades. One way to express this effect is to generate a sequence that decreases as k increases and that weights the effects of the input on the output differently according to elapsed time. Proceeding in this way, let $w : \mathbb{Z}_+ \rightarrow (0, 1]$ be the decreasing sequence with $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} w(k) = 0$, based on which the following weighted norm is defined

$$\|u\|_w \triangleq \sup_{k \leq 0} |u(k)| w(-k). \quad (3.5)$$

It is easy to see that the practical effect of norm 3.5 is to make the input $u(k)$ fade or vanish as $k \rightarrow -\infty$. With these elements it is now possible to define the concept of fading memory.

Definición 9 (Fading Memory). A causal operator $N : l^\infty \rightarrow l^\infty$ has fading memory in

$\mathbf{K} \subset l^\infty$ if given $\varepsilon > 0$ there exist: 1) a decreasing sequence $w : \mathbb{Z}_+ \rightarrow (0, 1]$ with $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} w(k) = 0$ and 2) $\delta > 0$, such that for each $u, v \in \mathbf{K}$

$$\sup_{k \leq 0} |u(k) - v(k)| w(-k) < \varepsilon \implies |Nu(0) - Nv(0)| < \delta. \quad (3.6)$$

The previous definition expresses conceptually how the system output is influenced less and less by remote input signals. The *weight function* $w(k)$ simulates making the remote past of the input fade away, annulling it in the limit. From comparison of equations 3.6 and 3.4 it is easy to see that if an operator has fading memory it is also continuous, i.e., fading memory can be interpreted as a more “physical” form of continuity. However, the converse is not valid, as shown in the following example of an operator that is continuous but does not have fading memory.

Example 4 (*Peak Detector Operator*). : Let $N_{dp} : l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow l^\infty(\mathbb{Z})$ be the peak detector operator defined as

$$N_{dp}u(k) = \sup_{n \leq k} u(n),$$

which retains the peak value of the input signal. It is easy to see that the operator N_{dp} does not have fading memory, since regardless of what happens in its past, the output retains the maximum value of the input signal. If the input sequence contained a single nonzero value, say $u_0 = 1$, the output would indefinitely maintain the value $N_{dp}u(k) = 1$. However, the operator N_{dp} is continuous, which follows from seeing that for all $u, v \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z})$

$$\|N_{dp}u - N_{dp}v\|_\infty \leq \|u - v\|_\infty.$$

Note that N_{dp} operates on discrete sequences even though the plot of Figure 3.4 uses continuous signals for ease of visualization. ■

The concepts and definitions necessary to understand the approximation capabilities of the LNet structure have now been presented; these capabilities are proved in the theorem of the following section.

Figure 3.4: Peak Detector Operator.

3.3 LNet Structure Approximation Theorem

This section states the theorem establishing the approximation capabilities of the LNet structure. A version of this theorem was preliminarily proved by Sentoni et al. [65]; the complete version follows.

Theorem 3 (LNet Structure). *Let \mathbf{K} be a ball in l^∞ , $\mathbf{K} \triangleq \{u \in l^\infty \mid \|u\| \leq m_1\}$, with $m_1 > 0$, and let $N : l^\infty \rightarrow l^\infty$ be any time-invariant, causal operator with fading memory in \mathbf{K} . Then there exist a set of m Laguerre operators $\{L_0(\cdot), L_1(\cdot), \dots, L_{m-1}(\cdot)\}$ and a single hidden layer Perceptron $NN(\cdot)$, such that for all $u \in \mathbf{K}$*

$$\|Nu - \tilde{N}u\| \leq \varepsilon,$$

where $\tilde{N}u$ is given by

$$\tilde{N}u(k) = NN(L_0u(k), L_1u(k), \dots, L_{m-1}u(k)),$$

where $NN(\cdot)$ is a single hidden layer Perceptron with m inputs and no neurons expressed by 2.5, and the Laguerre systems are taken according to 1.15.

The steps involved in the proof of the LNet theorem, which are outlined in Table 3.1, are now described. We are interested in proving that the LNet operator \tilde{N} is capable of approximating any nonlinear, time-invariant, causal operator N possessing fading memory. This operator N has an associated functional F , just as the operators

	Theorem Involved	Result Obtained
1	<i>Stone-Weierstrass Theorem</i> 1.1 <i>Lemma I</i> 1.2 <i>Lemma II</i> 1.3 <i>Lemma III</i>	$ Fu - \tilde{F}u \leq \varepsilon_1$ Compactness of \mathbf{K}_- w.r.t. $\ u\ _w$ $\{G_i\}$ continuous w.r.t. $\ u\ _w$ $\{G_i\}$ separates points in $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$
2	<i>Cybenko's Theorem</i>	$ Fu - \tilde{F}u \leq \varepsilon_2$
3	<i>Recover operator \tilde{N}</i>	$\ Nu - \tilde{N}u\ \leq \varepsilon$

Table 3.1: Scheme of Theorems and Results Involved in the Proof of the LNet Theorem.

$L_i(\cdot)$ have their corresponding associated functionals G_i . Item 1) of the table indicates the beginning of the proof, which uses a version of the Stone-Weierstrass Theorem, expressing that any continuous functional F can be approximated arbitrarily well on a compact space² \mathbf{E} , by a polynomial combination of a set \mathbf{G} of continuous functionals that separate points in said compact set. To use this theorem as a tool, it is necessary to first prove the lemmas indicated in the table as 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3, which establish that: the involved space is compact with respect to the norm $\|\cdot\|_w$ (see [6]), the functionals G_i used separate points in \mathbf{E} , and that they are continuous with respect to $\|\cdot\|_w$.

Once these three lemmas have been proved, the hypotheses of the Stone-Weierstrass Theorem are satisfied, by which it is proved that the functional \tilde{F} associated with the LNet operator \tilde{N} can approximate any functional in the compact space \mathbf{E} by means of a combination of discrete Laguerre systems implemented by a polynomial $p(\cdot)$.

This step in the proof is indicated by item 2) of Table 3.1. Using Theorem 1, it is shown that in turn the polynomial $p(\cdot)$ can be approximated by a neural network $NN(\cdot)$.

At this point, indicated as 3) in Table 3.1, it is possible to complete the proof by recovering the LNet operator \tilde{N} from its associated functional via equation 3.3. The table helps follow the proof by indicating which theorem is used and what result is obtained; we therefore begin by stating the Stone-Weierstrass Theorem.

²A metric space \mathbf{E} is compact if and only if it is totally bounded and complete [31, Teorema 2, pag 100]. Since \mathbf{E} is complete, every Cauchy sequence in it has a limit. Consequently, a metric space \mathbf{E} is compact if and only if from every infinite sequence in \mathbf{E} one can extract a subsequence that also converges in \mathbf{E} .

Example: a subset M of R^n is compact if and only if it is closed and bounded.

3.3.1 Stone-Weierstrass Theorem

Theorem 4 (*Stone-Weierstrass*). *Let \mathbf{E} be a compact metric space and let \mathbf{G} be a set of continuous functionals on E that separate points, i.e., for any $u, v \in \mathbf{E}$ there exists $G \in \mathbf{G}$ such that $Gu \neq Gv$. Then given $\varepsilon > 0$ and any continuous functional F on \mathbf{E} , there exist a polynomial $p : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and functionals $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_m\} \in \mathbf{G}$ such that for all $u \in \mathbf{E}$*

$$|Fu - p(G_1u, G_2u, \dots, G_mu)| < \varepsilon.$$

As indicated by Table 3.1, three lemmas must be proved, denoted I, II and III, which specifically state that:

1. The space \mathbf{K}_- defined by B.1 with the norm $\|u\|_w$ is compact in $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$.
2. The set of functionals G_i associated with the discrete Laguerre operators is continuous with respect to the norm $\|u\|_w$.
3. The set of functionals G_i separates points in $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$.

We now proceed to prove the following Lemma.

3.3.2 Lemma I

Lemma 1. *Since the proof of this lemma follows the general lines of the one proved in [6], the proof is included as Appendix B.*

3.3.3 Lemma II

Lemma 2. *The set of functionals G_n associated with the discrete Laguerre operators is continuous with respect to the weighted norm $\|\cdot\|_w$ of equation 3.5.*

Proof. Consider the set of functionals $\mathbf{G} = \{G_0, G_1, \dots\}$, where $G_n u = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} l_n(i) u(-i)$ is the functional associated with the operator $L_n(\cdot)$. We say that the weight function $w'(i)$ dominates $w(i)$ if $w'(i) \geq w(i)$ for all i . If a dominating sequence $w'(i)$ is found, one simply chooses $w(i) = w'(i)$ and the proof is unchanged. Furthermore, it has been proved that if a system has fading memory under a weighted norm, it also has fading

memory for all weighting sequences [42]. Therefore let $w(i) = 1/(1+i)$ be the weight function; then

$$\begin{aligned}
|G_n u - G_n v| &= \left| \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} l_n(i) u(-i) - \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} l_n(i) v(-i) \right|, \\
|G_n u - G_n v| &\leq \sup_{i \geq 0} (|u(-i) - v(-i)| w(i)) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} |l_n(i)| w(i)^{-1}, \\
|G_n u - G_n v| &\leq \|u(-i) - v(-i)\|_w \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} |l_n(i)| w(i)^{-1}. \tag{3.7}
\end{aligned}$$

The Laguerre systems are exponentially stable as proved in Appendix A; therefore, by equation A.1, the last term in equation 3.7 can be expressed as:

$$\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} |l_n(i)| w(i)^{-1} \leq (n+1) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} r^i (i+1), \quad |a| < r < 1.$$

Let

$$S(r, N) = \sum_{i=0}^N r^i = \frac{1 - r^{N+1}}{1 - r}. \tag{3.8}$$

Taking the derivative of the first term in 3.8,

$$\frac{d}{dr} \sum_{i=0}^N r^i = \sum_{i=0}^N \frac{d}{dr} r^i = r^{-1} \sum_{i=0}^N i r^i, \tag{3.9}$$

the derivative of the second term in 3.8

$$\frac{d}{dr} \frac{1 - r^{N+1}}{1 - r} = \frac{1 - r^{N+1}}{(1 - r)^2}, \tag{3.10}$$

and equating we obtain

$$\sum_{i=0}^N r^i (i+1) = \frac{1 - 2r^{N+1} + r^{N+2}}{(1 - r)^2}. \tag{3.11}$$

Using this last equation we can bound

$$|G_n^N u - G_n^N v| \leq \|u(-i) - v(-i)\|_w (n+1) \frac{1 - 2r^{N+1} + r^{N+2}}{(1 - r)^2}, \tag{3.12}$$

where the functional $G_n^N u = \sum_{i=0}^N l_n(i) u(-i)$ uses only N terms of the impulse response $l_n(i)$. Taking the limit as $N \rightarrow \infty$, i.e., considering the full infinite impulse response, we obtain

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} |G_n^N u - G_n^N v| = |G_n u - G_n v| \leq \|u(-i) - v(-i)\|_w \frac{(n+1)}{(1-r)^2}. \quad (3.13)$$

Then given $\varepsilon > 0$, choosing $\|u(-i) - v(-i)\|_w < \delta = \varepsilon(1-r^2)/(n+1)$, by equation 3.13

$$|G_n u - G_n v| < \varepsilon,$$

which proves Lemma 2. □

3.3.4 Lemma III

Lemma 3. *The set of functionals G_n separates points in $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$.*

Proof. We must prove that the set of functionals G_n separates points in $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$, i.e., for any $u_1, u_2 \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$ there exists G_n such that $G_n u_1 \neq G_n u_2$. If they do not separate points, it means that for $u_1, u_2 \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$ there exists G_n such that $G_n u_1 = G_n u_2$ for all n . Let $u = u_1 - u_2$, so that $G_n u = 0$ for all n . It suffices to show that $u = 0$ (the null sequence), which will prove that the discrete Laguerre functionals separate points in $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$. The G_n can be expressed as

$$G_n u = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} l_n(i) a^{-i/2} a^{i/2} u(-i) = 0$$

where a is the generating pole of the Laguerre systems 1.15. It is easy to see that the elements $(u(-i) a^{i/2})$ and $(l_n(i) a^{-i/2})$ belong to $l^2(\mathbb{Z}_+)$. Since the set of functions $\{l_n(i) a^{-i/2}\}$ forms a basis for $l^2(\mathbb{Z}_+)$ and is non-null, we conclude that $u(-i) a^{i/2} = 0$ and therefore $u = 0$. Expressed differently, since no combination of functionals G_n can generate the null sequence, the only way that $G_n u = 0$ is if $u = 0$. This proves that the discrete Laguerre functionals separate points in $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$, proving Lemma 3. □

3.3.5 Proof of the LNet Structure Theorem

Proof. Applying Theorem 4 of Stone-Weierstrass, and using Lemmas 1, 2 and 3, we can conclude that every functional F associated with a nonlinear, time-invariant operator possessing fading memory can be approximated by a set of functionals associated with the Laguerre systems, followed by a polynomial $p(\cdot)$, as

$$|Fu - p(G_0u, G_1u, \dots, G_{m-1}u)| < \varepsilon/2, \quad \text{with } \varepsilon_1 > 0.$$

This polynomial must now be approximated by a neural network; given $\varepsilon_2 > 0$, by Theorem 1 there exists a single hidden layer Perceptron $NN(\cdot)$ for which

$$|NN(x) - p(x)| < /2.$$

Since $u \in \mathbf{K} \implies \|u\|_w \leq m_1$, it is easy to see that $|x_i| < \|L_{i-1}u\|_w \leq c_i$, $c_i > 0$, $i : 1, \dots, m$. Setting $\xi_i = x_i/c_i$, $i : 1, \dots, m$ it is easy to see that $\xi_i \in I_n$ and $p(\xi) \in C(I_n)$. Therefore, given $\varepsilon > 0$, by Theorem 1, there exists a network $NN(\xi)$ that approximates $p(\xi)$ arbitrarily well and for which

$$|Fu - NN(G_0u, G_1u, \dots, G_{m-1}u)| < \varepsilon. \quad (3.14)$$

At this point it has been proved that every functional F associated with a nonlinear, time-invariant, causal operator possessing fading memory can be approximated by a set of functionals associated with Laguerre systems followed by a single hidden layer Perceptron $NN(\cdot)$. To prove that it can approximate any operator with fading memory, equation 3.3 is used to recover the operators associated in equation 3.14. Let $k \in \mathbb{Z}$; then $Pq^k u \in \mathbf{K}_-$, and

$$|FPq^k u - NN(G_0Pq^k u, G_1Pq^k u, \dots, G_{m-1}Pq^k u)| = |Nu(k) - \tilde{N}u(k)| < \varepsilon.$$

Since this last equation is valid for all $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, we conclude that for all $u \in \mathbf{K}$

$$\|Nu - \tilde{N}u\| < \varepsilon,$$

which concludes the proof. □

This theorem ensures that the class of discrete, causal, nonlinear systems with fading memory can be approximated by the LNet structure. In the following section, certain remarks are made on the class of approximation obtained.

3.4 Remarks on the Obtained Approximation

It has been shown that for a system to be approximable by the LNet structure, only a few physically reasonable assumptions are required: being causal, time-invariant, and possessing fading memory. The concept of fading memory is associated with a characteristic of the operator representing the input-output system. However, it is possible that no input-output operator representing the system exists; but if the system has fading memory, it can be approximated by an LNet structure.

It is known that all physical systems have some degree of saturation. Figure 3.5 shows various types of saturation commonly found in physical systems. The LNet structure has approximation capabilities similar to those of a Volterra series. However, the LNet structure outperforms the Volterra series in the number of parameters required to achieve an equivalent approximation, an advantage that grows when the system exhibits some form of saturation as most physical systems do [43]. This advantage is related to those possessed by a single hidden layer Perceptron for approximating continuous functions, as expressed in previous sections.

Figure 3.5: Various Types of Saturation.

The characterization of systems possessing fading memory continues to be a topic of active study, as pointed out by Shamma [67]. Some examples of fading-memory

systems include linear systems, cascades of linear dynamic systems with static nonlinearities (Wiener and Hammerstein models), and nonlinear systems with unique steady state. For example, if at an equilibrium point the vector field is continuously differentiable and the linearized system at that point is exponentially stable and controllable, then for sufficiently small inputs the operator relating the input to the states has fading memory.

3.5 Conclusions

It has been shown that the LNet structure is capable of approximating nonlinear, discrete, causal, time-invariant operators possessing fading memory. The approximation is performed on the operator that represents the system from the input-output viewpoint. To prove the approximation capabilities of the LNet structure, the necessary concepts were defined, among which fading memory plays a central role. It was shown that this concept can be viewed as a certain form of continuity of the operator associated with the system. The chapter concluded with a discussion of the obtained results. The following chapter addresses the methods for identifying the parameters of this structure.

Chapter 4

Determination of the LNET Structure

This chapter presents the methodology for determining the LNet structure: the number of Laguerre systems and the number of neurons in the hidden layer. The use of the so-called Lipschitz coefficients, grounded in the continuity of the LNet operator, will serve to evaluate the number of systems. For estimating the number of hidden layer neurons, a variation of pruning techniques is used; this technique is based on a singular value decomposition of the data matrix propagated through the hidden layer. The chapter concludes, after presenting the methods for validating the obtained model, with a discussion of the material covered and some general remarks.

4.1 Introduction

This chapter develops the identification procedure for the LNet structure of order (m, no) shown in Figure 2.12, for m Laguerre systems and a Perceptron with no neurons in the hidden layer. In general, constructing a model from data involves three basic components: data collection, the candidate model set, and rules by which a model from this set can be determined using the collected data.

In certain situations the input-output data can be collected through an identification experiment. In such cases it is possible to define which signals are measurable, when to measure them, and even what type of input signals to use. The objective of designing the experiment, subject to existing constraints, is to make appropriate decisions so that the collected data provide as much information as possible. When it is not possible to design the data collection experiment, data from the normal operation of the

system must be used. Even so, the data obtained must contain sufficient information to obtain a “good enough” model from the candidate model set.

The candidate model set is determined when the collection of models from which an appropriate one is expected to be found is specified. We will use the set of LNet models, which as proved in the previous chapter, is capable of uniformly approximating the class of discrete, shift-invariant, causal nonlinear systems possessing fading memory. Each LNet structure is defined by a set of m Laguerre systems generated by the pole a and a single hidden layer Perceptron with no neurons. The expansion pole can be estimated as:

$$a = 1 - T/t_d, \quad (4.1)$$

where t_d is the dominant time constant of the system and T is the sampling period (for discrete systems $T = 1$). It will be assumed that this constant is known or can be easily estimated [80]. A simple method that can be used consists of sampling the system step response and then approximating that response in some optimal sense using the low-pass term $L_0(q^{-1})$ of the Laguerre systems. Once the pole a has been estimated, the Laguerre system set is fully defined, leaving only the evaluation of the number m of such systems and the number no of neurons in the Perceptron hidden layer.

The number m of systems will be evaluated based on the concept of continuity of the LNet operator. Since this operator is continuous, so too must be the nonlinear transformation produced by the Perceptron. Based on this concept, an index is defined, called the Lipschitz coefficient, which serves to evaluate the continuity of the involved function. The information thus obtained is useful for estimating the required number of systems, after which only the number of hidden layer neurons remains to be evaluated.

To bound the number of hidden layer neurons, a technique based on the pruning concept introduced by Sentoni et al. [63] is used. This technique consists of beginning training with an overabundant number of neurons and then, through a singular value analysis of the hidden layer data, bounding the number no of neurons in that layer. After this is done, the training process continues to identify the values of the neural network parameters.

Once the LNet structure is defined by its order (m, no) and the pole value a , it only remains to determine the values of its parameters. These are the input layer weight matrix $\mathbf{W1} : (m \times no)$ and its bias vector $\mathbf{b1} : (no \times 1)$, together with the

output layer weight vector $\mathbf{w}_2 : (1 \times no)$ and the value b_2 . To obtain these values, an optimization algorithm is used to minimize a specific criterion such as the output error. After completing identification, a model $\tilde{\Sigma}$ of order (m, no) (not necessarily unique) is obtained that uniformly approximates the system Σ in the subset \mathbf{K} of l^∞ , \mathbf{K} given by equation 1.21. This model is the one that best describes the data according to the chosen criterion. It only remains to verify whether this particular model is “good enough”, i.e., whether it is valid for its intended purpose. The set of techniques used to perform this verification is known as model validation. This process involves several steps for checking how the model relates to the observed data, to prior knowledge, and to the use that one intends to make of it. The poor performance of a model is always in relation to these concepts, while good performance is always associated with a certain degree of confidence. Thus, a model should never be accepted as a final and complete description of the system; at most it should be conceived as a sufficiently good description of certain aspects of the system that are of particular interest. This gives an idea of how iterative an identification process really is.

Stated in this way, the process of identifying a system has a natural flow: first collect the data, then select the model structure, and finally estimate the parameters of the best model for that structure. It is quite probable that the first model obtained will not pass the validation tests. In such cases one must go back and revise several steps of the procedure. The model may be deficient for several reasons:

- The numerical procedure used was unable to find the best model according to the chosen criterion.
- The criterion may not have been correctly chosen.
- The model structure may not have been appropriate, i.e., it contains no description that is good enough for the system.
- The data do not contain the amount of information necessary to carry out the identification.

Most of an identification process involves the iterative resolution—guided by experience gained in previous steps—of the problems raised by the points just mentioned [39]. With this introduction complete, the technique for estimating the required number m of Laguerre systems will now be developed.

4.2 Evaluation of the Number of Laguerre Systems

The LNet structure represents an operator with fading memory that, as established in Chapter III, is a generalization of continuous operators. This operator continuously transforms input signals into output signals through the composition of two transformations: that produced by the Laguerre systems followed by that of the Perceptron. The single hidden layer Perceptron produces a continuous, multivariable transformation over a given region of the signals provided by the Laguerre systems:

$$\tilde{y}(k) = Nu(k) = NN(L_0u(k), L_1u(k), \dots, L_{m-1}u(k)).$$

Each individual transformation is continuous; therefore so must be their composition. The technique for determining the number of systems is based on the possibility of evaluating how the continuity of the LNet operator varies with the number m of systems used. For simplicity we denote the LNet structure as

$$\tilde{y}_k = g(\mathbf{z}_k) = g([z_1(k), z_2(k), \dots, z_m(k)]), \quad (4.2)$$

where $g(\cdot)$ represents the Perceptron and \mathbf{z}_k is a row vector of dimension $[1 \times m]$

$$\mathbf{z}_k = [z_1(k), z_2(k), \dots, z_m(k)], \quad (4.3)$$

where each component $z_j(k) = L_{j-1}u(k)$ represents the input signal $u(k)$ filtered by the $(j-1)$ -th Laguerre system. Let $\mathbf{Z} : [np \times m]$ be the matrix in which the np available data points are grouped:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{z}_1 \\ \mathbf{z}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{z}_k \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{z}_{np} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.4)$$

where each \mathbf{z}_k is composed of the vector of equation 4.3 for $k : 1, \dots, np$. Once the pole value a specifying the complete Laguerre system set is determined, the signals $z_j(k)$ can be computed. The number m of systems used is reflected in the dimension of the domain

	z_1	z_2	z_3	y
a)	0	0	0	1
b)	0	ϵ	1	0

Table 4.1: Values of the Function over the Complete Data Set.

of the function $g(\cdot)$. For example, if $m = 1$, $g(\cdot) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$; if $m = 2$, $g(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$; and in general $g(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. The problem of estimating the number of systems can be seen as estimating the dimension for which the unknown function $g(\cdot)$ is continuous—that is, which “nearby” points in the input space that take values from the matrix \mathbf{Z} must be mapped by $g(\cdot)$ to “nearby” points in the output space. The following example will clarify this concept.

Example 5. *Suppose we want to estimate the dimension of the domain of a continuous function $g : [0, 1]^3 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ from the data illustrated by Table 4.1 where $\epsilon > 0$ is an infinitesimal. If only the signals z_1 and z_2 were used, the distance in the input space would be*

$$\|\mathbf{z}_a - \mathbf{z}_b\|_2^2 = (z_{1a} - z_{1b})^2 + (z_{2a} - z_{2b})^2 = \epsilon^2,$$

which is infinitesimal, where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the 2-norm in Euclidean space. According to the concept of continuous function, two points close in the input space must be mapped to nearby points in the output space. The distance in the output space is

$$\|y_a - y_b\|_2^2 = 1,$$

resulting in widely separated points, since the function $g(\cdot)$ maps points of the unit cube $[0, 1]^3$ (where the maximum distance is $\sqrt{3}$) into the segment $[0, 1]$. However, when the correct number of 3 dimensions is used, the distance between the two points in the input space is

$$\|\mathbf{z}_a - \mathbf{z}_b\|_2^2 = (z_{1a} - z_{1b})^2 + (z_{2a} - z_{2b})^2 + (z_{3a} - z_{3b})^2 = 1 + \epsilon^2,$$

which indicates that the points in the input space are no longer nearby, and a continuous function passing through them can be established. ■

The concept illustrated by the previous example suggests a first method for determining the dimension of the input space, based on the continuity of the function $g(\cdot)$ to be estimated. Assuming the amount of data (\mathbf{z}_k, y_k) , $k : 1, \dots, np$ available to

estimate the dimension of $g(\cdot)$ is sufficient, one proceeds as follows:

1. Start with $m = 1$.
2. Verify by definition the continuity of the function $g(\cdot)$ for the complete set of available data.

That is, given $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $\delta > 0$ such that for every pair of points $(i, j) : 1, \dots, np$ in the input space,

$$\|z_i - z_j\| \leq \delta \implies |y_i - y_j| < \varepsilon.$$

3. Is the function $g(\cdot)$ continuous? **Yes**, then m is the desired value. **Stop**.
4. **No**, set $m = m + 1$ and return to #1.

The previous algorithm proposes a first approach to the problem of verifying the continuity of the unknown function $g(\cdot)$ from the available data [62]. While simple in conception and effective when no measurement noise is present, the method fails when noise is present. Moreover, it is difficult to determine the ε and δ that indicate what “nearby” means in the input and output spaces respectively. A refinement of this method consists of using the so-called Lipschitz coefficients.

4.2.1 Lipschitz Coefficients

A continuous function taking values in a closed region is Lipschitz bounded. Based on this principle, Xiangdong and Asada [78] introduced the Lipschitz coefficients method for evaluating the dimension of a multivariate function $g(\cdot)$ in nonlinear input-output models. We now define what is meant by the Lipschitz condition.

Definición 10. *We say that the function $g(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is Lipschitz bounded in a ball centered at \mathbf{z}_o , $\mathbf{B} = \{\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^m : \|\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{z}_o\| \leq r > 0\}$, if there exists a finite constant k_{lip} such that*

$$|g(\mathbf{z}_i) - g(\mathbf{z}_j)| \leq k_{lip} \|\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_j\|_i, \forall \mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{z}_j \in \mathbf{B}, \quad (4.5)$$

where k_{lip} is known as the Lipschitz constant and $\|\cdot\|_i$ represents an arbitrary norm in the input space.

For the specific case of a single hidden layer Perceptron, [72] proves that the transformation produced by the network is Lipschitz bounded, i.e., satisfies equation 4.5. A function satisfying condition 4.5 has bounded partial derivatives [74, p. 45]:

$$|g_j| = |\partial g / \partial z_j| \leq k_{lip}, \quad j : 1, \dots, m. \quad (4.6)$$

The Lipschitz coefficients λ_{ij} are then defined as

$$\lambda_{ij} = \frac{|y_i - y_j|}{\|\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_j\|}, \quad (i \neq j),$$

where $y_i = g(\mathbf{z}_i)$ by equation 4.2, for $i, j : 1, \dots, np$. These quotients express the ratio of two quantities: $\|\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_j\|$, the distance between two points in the input space, and $\|\delta y\| = |y_i - y_j|$, the difference between the values $g(\mathbf{z}_i)$ and $g(\mathbf{z}_j)$. Since the function $g(\cdot)$ is continuous, the Lipschitz condition requires that the Lipschitz quotients be bounded:

$$0 \leq \lambda_{ij} = \frac{|y_i - y_j|}{\|\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_j\|} < \infty.$$

Applying sensitivity analysis to the input-output formulation of equation 4.2 we obtain

$$\delta y = g_1 \delta z_1 + g_2 \delta z_2 + \dots + g_m \delta z_m,$$

where $\delta y = g(\mathbf{z}_i) - g(\mathbf{z}_j)$ and the g_i denoted by equation 4.6 are the partial derivatives of $g(\mathbf{z}_i)$ from 4.2 with respect to each component i . Then

$$\lambda_{ij} = \frac{|\delta y|}{\sqrt{(\delta z_1)^2 + (\delta z_2)^2 + \dots + (\delta z_m)^2}} = \frac{|g_1 \delta z_1 + g_2 \delta z_2 + \dots + g_m \delta z_m|}{\sqrt{(\delta z_1)^2 + (\delta z_2)^2 + \dots + (\delta z_m)^2}}.$$

According to the previous definitions, taking $\delta = \max_{i \in (1, \dots, m)} |\delta_i|$ and $|g_i| \leq k_{lip}$, the bound on the Lipschitz quotients can be obtained via the Schwarz inequality:

$$\lambda_{ij}^m = k_{lip} \frac{|\delta z_1| + |\delta z_2| + \dots + |\delta z_m|}{\sqrt{(\delta z_1)^2 + (\delta z_2)^2 + \dots + (\delta z_m)^2}} \leq k_{lip} \sqrt{m}, \quad (4.7)$$

where the superscript m in λ_{ij}^m represents the number of Laguerre systems used. Let m_0 be the desired number of Laguerre systems. Therefore, if all variables z_i , $i : 1, \dots, m_0$ are

included in the reconstruction of the unknown function $g(\mathbf{z})$, the Lipschitz quotients for all data pairs (\mathbf{z}_i, y_i) will be bounded. Two possible situations can arise: if some variable is absent from the reconstruction, the Lipschitz quotients will be arbitrarily large; while if more variables than necessary are included, these coefficients will be bounded. This is clarified below.

1. $m < m_0$, i.e., the number used m is less than the desired number m_0 .

We want to show that if any variable is absent from the reconstruction, the Lipschitz quotients will be arbitrarily large. To this end, assume without loss of generality that the variable z_{m_0} is not included in the reconstruction of the unknown function $g(\cdot)$. Assume further that for some pair i, j of the available data we have $\delta z_1 = \dots = \delta z_{m_0-1} = 0$ and $\delta z_{m_0} = \epsilon$, an infinitesimal. We now evaluate the Lipschitz quotients, verifying that with z_{m_0} absent the Lipschitz coefficients are arbitrarily large, and with z_{m_0} present the coefficient is bounded. The distance in the output space is the same in both cases,

$$\delta y = y_i - y_j,$$

since it is a given. The distance in the input space with z_{m_0} absent is

$$\sqrt{(\delta z_1)^2 + (\delta z_2)^2 + \dots + (\delta z_{m_0-1})^2}.$$

Under these conditions the Lipschitz coefficient $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0-1}$ is

$$\lambda_{ij}^{m_0-1} = \frac{|\delta y|}{\sqrt{(\delta z_1)^2 + (\delta z_2)^2 + \dots + (\delta z_{m_0-1})^2}} = \frac{|g_{m_0}| \epsilon}{\sqrt{(\delta z_1)^2 + (\delta z_2)^2 + \dots + (\delta z_{m_0-1})^2}} \rightarrow \infty.$$

However, if the variable z_{m_0} is included in the reconstruction, the coefficient $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0}$ is

$$\lambda_{ij}^{m_0-1} = |g_{m_0}|.$$

It is easy to see that $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0-1}$ (with z_{m_0} excluded) will be much larger than $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0}$ (in which all variables are included).

1. $m > m_0$, i.e., the number used m is greater than the desired number m_0 .

When a redundant variable z_{m_0+1} has been included, from the previous analysis it is easy to see that $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0+1}$ will be only slightly smaller than $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0}$, but not significantly so.

Figure 4.1: Typical Curve of the Lipschitz Coefficients.

The preceding discussion provides the basis for identifying the number of inputs using the information provided by the Lipschitz quotients. Proceeding toward this objective, the following index is defined

$$\lambda^m = \left(\prod_{k=1}^{mv} \sqrt{m} \lambda^m(k) \right)^{1/mv}, \quad (4.8)$$

where $mv = cte \cdot np$, $cte \in [.01, .02]$, $\lambda^m(k)$ is the k -th largest Lipschitz coefficient calculated with the variables (z_1, \dots, z_m) among all λ_{ij}^m of Eq. 4.7 ($i \neq j$; $i, j: 1, \dots, np$). The index of equation 4.8 is defined as the geometric mean of the mv largest values of λ_{ij}^m to reduce the effect of any noise present. From the previous analysis one can see that if λ^{m_0} is the desired number of variables, λ^{m_0+1} is very close to $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0}$. However, $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0-1}$ is much larger than $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0}$, and $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0-2}$ is much larger than $\lambda_{ij}^{m_0-1}$. If a curve is plotted showing the value of λ^m on the ordinate and m on the abscissa, it can be observed (see Figure 4.1) that starting from a given point that we define as λ^{m_0} , the curve enters a saturation region. It is easy to see that if m smaller than m_0 is selected, λ^m will increase significantly, whereas if $m > m_0$ is selected, no significant decrease in λ^m is obtained.

Thus in the selection process it is convenient to take a cutoff constant γ such that m_0 can be selected as:

$$m_0 = \min_m [\lambda^m / \lambda^{m+1} < \gamma]. \quad (4.9)$$

The above can be summarized in the following algorithm:

1. Start with $m = 1$.
2. Verify the continuity of the function $g(\cdot)$ for the complete set of np available data using the Lipschitz coefficients.

That is, given a cutoff constant γ , verify that the coefficients have entered the saturation zone indicated by

$$m_0 = \min_m [\lambda^m / \lambda^{m+1} < \gamma]$$

3. Is the function $g(\cdot)$ continuous? **Yes:** then m is the desired value m_0 . **Stop.**
4. **No:** set $m = m + 1$ and return to #1.

The method for estimating the number of Laguerre systems based on a concept related to the continuity of the LNet operator has been presented. Next, some aspects related to the signals used for identification will be addressed.

Remarks on the Signals Used for Computing the Coefficients

An important aspect of system identification is considering the type of excitation signal to use. These signals must be admissible by the system as inputs and must possess characteristics that make them useful for identification and subsequent model validation. For identifying linear systems it is necessary to use persistently exciting signals.¹ For nonlinear systems there are additional requirements for the excitation signal due to the inherent complexity of such systems. Not only must the signals fall within the frequency range of interest, but they must also possess appropriate amplitude levels to excite the system so that it manifests its nonlinear nature in various zones of its operating region.

¹For a linear system of order n , signals with normal or uniform distribution and a combination of n sinusoidal signals at different frequencies ensure persistent excitation.

It should be noted, as mentioned above, that the signals used must also be useful for model validation.

Billings and Voon [5] developed validation techniques for input-output models that require the excitation signals to have a symmetric probability distribution. PRBS (Pseudo Random Binary Signals) and signals with normal or uniform distributions satisfy this requirement. PRBS signals have been widely used in linear system identification, but are not appropriate for nonlinear system identification: PRBS signals vary only between two levels, which is frequently insufficient [38] since it does not provide the amplitude richness necessary for identification. Leontaritis and Billings [38] proposed using a uniformly distributed signal taking values within the ranges of interest for identification. However, such signals are often impractical: they may vary frequently between very different values. Similar difficulties arise with normally distributed signals. In [20] a signal is proposed whose amplitude varies according to a uniform distribution within the region of interest, and for which the probability of changing value at the end of each sampling instant can be specified. The ability to specify the probability of change at the end of

Figure 4.2: Equiprobable Signal for Three Different Probabilities pr .

each sampling interval allows adapting the rate of variation of the excitation signal to the

constraints of the system. We define as EquiProb (EP) the type of signal for which both amplitude and probability of change vary according to a uniform distribution. The EP signal is illustrated in Figure 4.2 for three different change probabilities pr : in **a**) $pr = .1$, in **b**) $pr = .5$ and in **c**) $pr = .9$. It is easy to see that the parameter pr adjusts the rate of change. An example is now presented illustrating the variation in the computation of the Lipschitz coefficients when signals with different probability distributions—uniform, normal, and EP—are used.

Example 6. *This example illustrates the use of Lipschitz coefficients for identifying the order of a FIR filter using three different excitation signals. The system is described by equation 1.13*

$$y(k) = \bar{\mathbf{b}}^T \mathbf{u}_{nu}(k),$$

where \mathbf{u}_{nu} is expressed by equation 1.8 with $n_u = 5$ for the following coefficients

$$\bar{\mathbf{b}} = \left[.9 \quad -.7 \quad .5 \quad -.5 \quad .1 \quad .1 \right]^T.$$

There are clearly 6 significant filter coefficients, and this should be the value identified by the Lipschitz coefficients. These coefficients were computed using 200 input-output samples for three signals with different probability distributions: one with uniform distribution, one with normal distribution, and one with EP distribution with $pr = .5$. Figure 4.3 shows the results obtained in the three cases. It is observed that the Lipschitz coefficients computed for both the uniform-distribution signal in part **a**) and the normal-distribution signal in part **b**) stabilize at a value of 4. In part **c**), the Lipschitz coefficients computed with the EP input signal can be seen. The first 6 values are not plotted as they equal ∞ , with the coefficients stabilizing at the value 7. This value is expected according to the analysis in the previous section, since beyond 7 the curve enters a saturation region. ■

This section presented the technique for estimating the number of Laguerre systems using the Lipschitz coefficients together with some remarks on the signals used for identification. The next section presents the methodology for estimating the number of hidden layer neurons of the Perceptron.

Figure 4.3: Lipschitz Coefficients for Different Distributions: a) Uniform, b) Normal, and c) EP.

4.3 Estimation of the Number of Neurons via Singular Values

This section presents the methodology for estimating the number of neurons no in the Perceptron's hidden layer, using a technique based on the singular value decomposition of the data matrix propagated through the hidden layer. Evaluating the singular values allows detecting the existence of linearly dependent columns in this matrix, which would indicate an excess of neurons. Such neurons do not add significant information but increase the number of parameters to be estimated, reducing the generalization capacity of the Perceptron. For this reason, it is desirable to obtain a good model with the smallest possible number of elements. There are basically two approaches to resolving this issue:

Inclusion Techniques. This type of technique starts from a network with a small number of hidden layer neurons, which is gradually increased until the desired precision is achieved without sacrificing generalization capability.

Pruning Techniques. This type of technique starts from an overabundant number of hidden layer neurons and, using some criterion, proceeds to “prune” or remove some neurons.

The method presented here falls into this latter category: starting from a large number of neurons, this number is reduced using as criterion the condition number of the data matrix propagated through the hidden layer. To accomplish this, we use a singular value decomposition technique presented by Sentoni et al. [63] and by Nebot et al. [51]. In [63] the singular value decomposition is used singular values to bound the number of hidden layer neurons in a network modeling a chaotic logistic function—results that will be reproduced in an example. In [51] the same singular value decomposition technique is used to determine the number of hidden layer neurons in the identification of a flexible robot arm using a neural network. In parallel, a variation of this methodology was published by Psychogios and Ungar [57].

Prior results show that for np training patterns it is sufficient to use $no = np - 1$ neurons in the hidden layer [61, 28]. However, these results were developed for pattern classification studies. When used in function estimation, they generally lead

to an overestimate of the number of neurons. Moreover, given this first approximation there are a varied number of factors that can influence the estimation and that cannot be determined prior to training. To estimate this parameter, np patterns are available of training patterns from which the matrix $\mathbf{Z} : [np \times m]$ is formed as in equation 4.4, composed of each input pattern forming a row. The remaining parameters of the network have the following dimensions: $\mathbf{W1} : [m \times no]$, $\mathbf{b1} : [no \times 1]$, $\mathbf{w2} : [no \times 1]$ and $b2 : [1 \times 1]$. We now express the weight and data matrices in a slightly different form to formulate the singular value decomposition problem more simply. In accordance with what was expressed, a unit vector is appended to the matrix \mathbf{Z} , which can be considered as a constant-value input as indicated in Section 2.2 (see Figure 2.2). Simultaneously, the vector $\mathbf{b1}$ is regrouped in the matrix $\mathbf{W1}$ in the following way

$$\mathbf{Z} = [\mathbf{Z} \ \mathbf{I}_{np}], \quad \mathbf{W1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W1} \\ \mathbf{b1}^T \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.10)$$

where $\mathbf{I}_{np} : [1 \times np]$ is a unit vector. Since this introduces no additional complexity and for clarity, these matrices will be denoted with the same name. The matrix \mathbf{X}_o resulting from propagating the data matrix \mathbf{Z} through the hidden layer is then defined as

$$\mathbf{X}_o = \phi(\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{W1}), \quad (4.11)$$

where $\mathbf{X}_o : [np \times no]$, no is the number of hidden neurons, np is the number of training patterns, and $\phi(\cdot)$ is the layer activation function, applied component-wise as in 2.2, where the activation function of each neuron is

$$\phi(x) = \frac{(1 - e^{-2x})}{(1 + e^{-2x})}. \quad (4.12)$$

Together, $\mathbf{b2} = b2\mathbf{I}_{np}$, with which the network transforms input patterns into output patterns as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{X}_o\mathbf{w2} + \mathbf{b2}, \quad (4.13)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{y}} : [np \times 1]$ is the network output vector. Figure 4.4 illustrates the reformulation and the dimensions of the matrices involved.

The training algorithm consists of an optimization algorithm that minimizes the

Figure 4.4: Matrices Involved in Training.

following functional

$$\min_{\Theta} \|\tilde{\mathbf{y}} - \mathbf{y}\|_2^2, \quad (4.14)$$

where Θ represents the weights and bias of the network $\mathbf{W1}$, $\mathbf{b1}$, $\mathbf{w2}$, and $b2$; $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}$ and \mathbf{y} are the vectors of the network-approximated and system outputs respectively. The back-error propagation minimization algorithm used will not be described since it is standard in the literature [58] and available in any commercial software package such as MatlabTM. Additionally, we will set $b2 = 0$ in equation 4.13 for the remainder of the development to simplify the exposition, so the output becomes

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{X}_o \mathbf{w2}. \quad (4.15)$$

This assumption does not constitute a limitation since both \mathbf{X}_o and $\mathbf{w2}$ can be modified using an argument similar to that presented in equation 4.10. We are now ready to describe the technique used to bound the number of hidden layer neurons, outlined as follows:

1. Start the training (minimization) process with an overabundant number of neurons.
2. Advance the training process for a certain period of time, after which it is stopped. Form the matrix \mathbf{X}_o of equation 4.11 using the obtained parameters.
3. Bound the number of hidden neurons no based on a singular value analysis of the matrix \mathbf{X}_o .

4. Continue training the Perceptron with no hidden neurons until completion.
5. Validate the network.

We now address how to bound the number of hidden neurons no based on a singular value analysis of the matrix \mathbf{X}_o . It has been argued that most of the training time of a Perceptron is required to adjust the output layer weights, since the parameters that adjust first are those of the hidden layer [36]. It is therefore expected that, even if these parameters have not fully converged, they are closer to convergence than the output layer parameters. This assumption is equivalent to saying that the matrix \mathbf{X}_o will change during training more slowly than \mathbf{w}_2 , making it possible to analyze the linear output transformation $\tilde{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{X}_o \mathbf{w}_2$ through the singular value decomposition of \mathbf{X}_o . Any matrix $\mathbf{X}_o : [np \times no]$ can be expressed via a singular value decomposition [52] as

$$\mathbf{X}_o = \mathbf{U}_o^T \cdot \mathbf{\Sigma}_o \cdot \mathbf{V}_o, \quad (4.16)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_o : [np \times no]$, $\mathbf{V}_o : [no \times no]$, and $\mathbf{\Sigma}_o : [no \times no]$. The matrix $\mathbf{\Sigma}_o = \text{diag} \{ \sigma_i \}$, $i : 1, \dots, no$, contains the so-called *singular values* of \mathbf{X}_o such that $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_{no} \geq 0$. If a matrix \mathbf{X}_o has $\text{rank} = r_o < no$, then $\sigma_{r_o+1} = \dots = \sigma_{no} = 0$. In practice σ_{r_o+1} will be significantly smaller than σ_{r_o} , implying that there are $no - r_o$ linearly dependent columns in \mathbf{X}_o . The information contributed by these $no - r_o$ linearly dependent columns is practically null and is directly related to the magnitude of the associated singular value². In this way it is possible to determine the condition number of the matrix \mathbf{X}_o through the analysis of the singular values σ_i , thereby avoiding a high condition number in \mathbf{X}_o by adjusting the number of hidden neurons. Thus the number of nonzero singular values provides valuable information about the number of hidden layer neurons. Values of σ_i close to zero indicate that a certain number of hidden neurons are in excess. Let \mathbf{w}_2 be the least-squares solution of equation 4.14 obtained through equations 4.15 and 4.16 as

$$\mathbf{w}_2 = \mathbf{V}_o^T [\text{diag} (1/\sigma_i)] \mathbf{U}_o \mathbf{y},$$

where $1/\sigma_i = 0$ for every σ_i very close to zero. This solution is numerically very robust

²Si la matriz $\mathbf{X}_o = \mathbf{U}_o^T \cdot \mathbf{\Sigma}_o \cdot \mathbf{V}_o$, $\mathbf{U}_o : [np \times no]$, $\mathbf{V}_o : [no \times no]$, $\mathbf{\Sigma}_o : [no \times no]$, $\mathbf{\Sigma}_o = \text{diag} \{ \sigma_i \}$, $i : 1, \dots, no$, es aproximada por una matriz de $\text{rango} = r_o < no$, $\mathbf{X}_o^{r_o} = \mathbf{U}_o^T \cdot \mathbf{\Sigma}_1 \cdot \mathbf{V}_o$, where $\mathbf{\Sigma}_1 = \text{diag} \{ \sigma_{1i} \}$, with $\sigma_{1i} = \sigma_i$ for $i : 1, \dots, r_o$ and $\sigma_{1i} = 0$ for $i > r_o$, so that $\|\mathbf{X}_o - \mathbf{X}_o^{r_o}\|_2 = \sigma_{r_o+1}$

and explicitly indicates that $no - r_o$ neurons are not being used, so the selected number of neurons is r_o . Once this number is determined, training continues for a network with r_o neurons. After training is complete, the obtained network is validated. Applying this methodology allows arriving at a compromise between the number of neurons and the quality of the approximation achieved. It is known that with more parameters, the generalization capabilities of a network deteriorate for the same amount of training data. An example will now be presented to clarify the proposed methodology.

Example 7. *This example is a reproduction of the one presented in [63]. Let the logistic function*

$$x[k+1] = \alpha x[k](1 - x[k]),$$

where α is a parameter and $k \geq 1$ is a discrete variable representing time. This equation represents the population dynamics of certain biological systems. The problem is to predict the value of $x[k+1]$ given the information about $x[k]$. This system is chaotic for some values of $\alpha > 3$. We consider $x[1] = .1$ and $\alpha = 4$, for which the system is recognized as chaotic [7]. We wish to predict $x[k+1]$ given the present value $x[k]$; to this end a vector of 50 values is generated as shown in Figure 4.5, of which the first

Figure 4.5: Chaotic Population Dynamics of a Biological System.

15 are used for training and the remaining ones for model validation. According to the previous discussion, using $no = np - 1$ neurons in the hidden layer should be sufficient to reproduce the np training values. A network with one input and 14 hidden neurons was therefore synthesized. Training was started and stopped after a certain period; the data matrix \mathbf{Z} was propagated to form the matrix \mathbf{X}_o , which has 15 rows and 14 columns ($np = 15$, $no = 14$). Decomposing \mathbf{X}_o into singular values as in equation 4.16, the

singular value matrix Σ_0 is obtained as

$$\Sigma_0 = \text{diag} \{15.811, 5.817, 0.274, 0.121, 0.005, 0.002, 0.000, \dots, 0.000\}.$$

According to the results of this section, it can be seen that only 2 neurons appear to be necessary. To evaluate the method's performance, four different networks were trained with $n_o = 1, 2, 5,$ and 14 hidden neurons using a back-error propagation algorithm with the same parameters in all four cases. The training algorithm was applied to the first 15 data points for approximately 100 iterations. Figure 4.6 illustrates the results obtained in these cases where it can be seen that for one neuron (part **a**) the absolute error

Figure 4.6: Approximation Error for the Chaotic System: 1, 2, 5 and 14 Hidden Neurons.

is comparable in magnitude to the data. Part **b** shows that the difference between the absolute approximation errors for the networks with 2, 5 and 14 neurons is not significant, although a larger number of neurons does yield a smaller error. Table ?? expresses the approximation error for the 4 cases. It can be seen that the error decreases approximately with a $1/n$ relationship, in accordance with the results of [3] given by equation 2.18. ■

Red	Error
$\ x_{1n} - x\ _2$	2.5569
$\ x_{2n} - x\ _2$	0.2577
$\ x_{5n} - x\ _2$	0.1921
$\ x_{14n} - x\ _2$	0.1157

Table 4.2: Approximation Error: 1, 2, 5 and 14 Neurons.

The methodology for evaluating the number m of Laguerre systems and the number no of hidden layer neurons of the Perceptron—the constitutive parameters of the LNet structure—has been presented. Once the desired model is obtained, it must be validated.

4.4 Validation

Model validation forms the final stage of an identification process. There are basically two complementary approaches to model validation:

Cross-validation. This approach consists of dividing the available data into two disjoint sets: α for training (see equation 2.19) and β for testing (see equation 2.20). The training set is used to obtain the model, while the test set is used to verify the model's generalization. This latter point, which is a research topic in itself, refers to the model's capability to correctly predict values not present in the test set. The training process begins with the data from the set α , using it to fit the model. As the training process advances, the training error decreases monotonically, while the test error decreases until a certain instant t_0 after which it begins to increase, as can be seen in Figure 4.7. This instant t_0 indicates when parameter overfitting begins to occur. In this way, the test dataset is used to evaluate how the fitted model generalizes and to prevent parameter overfitting.

Self-validation. This approach consists of verifying the correlation of certain signals—typically inputs, outputs, and residuals—from the training set α . This type of test provides valuable information about model structures and possible unmodeled terms. However, when used as the sole validation tool, it tends to produce overfitting of the training dataset. To alleviate this, indices similar to Akaike's Prediction

Figure 4.7: Training and Test Errors in a Typical Learning Process.

Index [48] have been used. These indices reward models with fewer parameters over those using a larger number.

Most quantitative or self-validation tests are based on the computation of certain correlations: it is verified whether the residuals are correlated with the input signals or with each other (autocorrelated). At this stage of the identification process, a model $\tilde{\Sigma}$ of system Σ is available such that for a random input process u applied simultaneously to $\tilde{\Sigma}$ and Σ , the difference $\xi = y - \tilde{y}$ between their outputs is a zero-mean i.i.d. (i.i.d.) and independent of the output process. This hypothesis must be verified using correlation tests. The correlation between any two variables u and y is defined as:

$$\phi_{uy}(\tau) = E[u(k)y(k-\tau)] = E[u(k+\tau)y(k)],$$

where $E[\cdot]$ denotes the mathematical expectation operator. When the amount of available data is finite, the expectation becomes the sample expectation, a sum over the np available values

$$\phi_{uy}(\tau) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^{np-\tau} u(k+\tau)y(k).$$

It is desirable to scale these coefficients such that $-1 \leq \hat{\phi}_{u/y}(\tau) \leq 1$; the correlation coefficient is then defined as

$$\hat{\phi}_{uy}(\tau) = \frac{1}{np} \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{np-\tau} u(k+\tau)y(k)}{\sqrt{\hat{\phi}_{uu}(0) \hat{\phi}_{yy}(0)}}.$$

For validating linear systems, first-order input-output and residual correlations are sufficient; however, for nonlinear systems it is necessary to define higher-order moments [5]. These are

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \phi_{\xi\xi}(\tau) = \delta(\tau) \\ \phi_{u\xi}(\tau) = 0 \quad \forall \tau \\ \phi_{\xi\xi u}(\tau) = E[\xi(k)\xi(k-1-\tau)u(k-1-\tau)] = 0 \quad \tau \geq 0, \\ \phi_{u^2\xi}(\tau) = 0 \quad \forall \tau \\ \phi_{u^2\xi^2}(\tau) = 0 \quad \forall \tau \end{array} \right. \quad (4.17)$$

where $u(k)$ is the input sequence, $y(k)$ and $\tilde{y}(k)$ are the output sequences of the system and model respectively, and $\xi(k) = y(k) - \tilde{y}(k)$ is the residual sequence at instant k , for $k : 1, \dots, np$. The prime on a variable indicates that its mean has been subtracted,

$$u'(k) = u(k) - \bar{u}.$$

If the number of data points np is sufficiently large, the standard deviation of the estimated correlation coefficients is $1/\sqrt{np}$. The 95% confidence interval is therefore $\pm 1.96/\sqrt{np}$. This value suggests that, at the 95% confidence level, the hypothesis that the model is valid cannot be rejected if the absolute value of the presented tests is below $1.96/\sqrt{np}$ [5]. These tests constitute a useful tool that, used together with cross-validation, allows qualitatively establishing how good a model is. The following section presents a summary of the proposed identification methodology.

4.5 Summary of the Modeling Methodology

It will be assumed that a sufficient number np of input-output data pairs $[u(k), y(k)]$, $k = 1, \dots, np$, are available to carry out the approximation. Then:

1. Evaluate the Laguerre system pole according to equation 4.1.
2. Evaluate the number m_0 of Laguerre systems using the Lipschitz coefficients λ .

Filter the available data using the Laguerre systems evaluated in step #1 to form the matrix $\mathbf{Z} : [np \times m]$ as in equation 4.4. Then evaluate m_0 using equation 4.9. The result is the matrix $\mathbf{Z} : [np \times m_0]$ with $\mathbf{z}(k) = [z_1(k), \dots, z_{m_0}(k)]$,

$k : 1, \dots, np$. Then begin the training process with the data set $(\mathbf{z}(k), y_k)$, $k : 1, \dots, np$.

3. Evaluate the number of hidden layer neurons using the singular value technique.

After the training process has run for some time, stop it and propagate the data matrix \mathbf{Z} through the hidden layer to obtain the matrix $\mathbf{X}_o = \phi(ZW_1)$. At this point the matrix $\mathbf{X}_o : [np \times no]$, where no is the number of hidden neurons and np is the number of training patterns. Decompose \mathbf{X}_o into singular values and select the appropriate number of hidden layer neurons according to the criterion stated in Section ??.

4. Continue training and validate the LNet structure.

4.6 Conclusions

This chapter presented the methodology for determining the LNet structure: the number of Laguerre systems and the number of hidden layer neurons. The use of the so-called Lipschitz coefficients, grounded in the continuity of the LNet operator, has proved to be a useful instrument for evaluating the number of systems. For estimating the number of hidden layer neurons, a variation of pruning techniques was used, based on a singular value decomposition of the data matrix propagated through the hidden layer. Finally, the procedures required to validate the obtained model were presented. The following chapter illustrates the application of the presented methodology through several examples.

Chapter 5

Application Examples

This chapter presents several examples illustrating the application of the presented modeling methodology, each highlighting specific aspects of modeling. The first example illustrates the capability of the methodology to find the correct structure for a discrete, time-invariant, causal nonlinear system with fading memory. The second presents a case of nonlinear echo cancellation to illustrate the advantages of the LNet structure over a Nonlinear FIR in terms of the number of terms required to approximate a given system. The last example considers the application of the proposed methodology to modeling a binary alcohol distillation column; within the modeling aspect, a possible MISO extension is considered and its results are presented. Additionally, design guidelines are presented for using the column LNet model in a predictive control strategy, and the chapter concludes with some general remarks.

5.1 Discrete Nonlinear System

This example illustrates the capability of the presented modeling methodology to obtain the correct structure for a discrete, time-invariant, causal nonlinear system with fading memory. The system of equation 5.1 evidently satisfies the above conditions and, by its structure, possesses a particular LNet representation: it can be thought of as the expansion of a linear system using Laguerre systems (whose coefficients are the weights of a single neuron) followed by a sigmoid function. The presented approximation methodology is applied to this system, and the approximations obtained by the LNet structure and the Korenberg parallel cascade structure are compared. For the LNet

model, results of structure evaluation in the presence of additive output noise are presented, and the example concludes with validation of the obtained model. The system to be used is described below.

5.1.1 System Description and Identification Conditions

Let the discrete nonlinear system, similar to that presented in [64], described by the following set of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} x(k+1) &= Ax(k) + Bu(k) \\ y(k) &= Cx(k) + Du(k) \\ yn(k) &= (1 + \exp(y(k) + 7))^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad , \quad (5.1)$$

where the matrices involved are shown below:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1.4 & -.61 & .084 \\ 1.0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1.0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, C = [1.6 \quad -.61 \quad .084]^T, D = [0].$$

It is clear that the system represented by equation set 5.1 has fading memory, since

Figure 5.1: Discrete Nonlinear System.

it is composed of a linear dynamic subsystem in cascade with a nonlinear transformation, as can be seen in Figure 5.1. It should be noted that the function $yn(k) = (1 + \exp(y(k) + 7))^{-1}$ involved is of sigmoid type. To proceed with identification, an input sequence of 300 values $\{u(k)\}_{k=1}^{300}$ was generated based on an Equiprob distribution with change probability $pr = .5$, scaled between $[-1, 1]$. By applying this sequence to the system and recording its output, the set of values $\{u(k), yn(k)\}_{k=1}^{300}$ was formed, of which the first 150 constituted the training set α and the last 150 the validation set β . With these sets the proposed approximation methodology was applied, yielding the following results.

5.1.2 Approximation Results

The first step of the approximation methodology is to evaluate the Laguerre system pole. A simple calculation shows that the eigenvalues of matrix A are $\text{eig}(A) = \{.7, .4, .3\}$. To demonstrate the robustness of the method with respect to the choice of pole, this parameter was selected as $a = .72$, a value very close to the dominant pole that the linear subsystem has at $.7$. Once this pole was evaluated, the data matrix $\mathbf{Z} : [150 \times 15]$ was formed as in equation 4.4 using the 150 training set α input values filtered by the systems $l_0(k), \dots, l_{14}(k)$. To evaluate the behavior of the methodology in the presence of additive output noise, noise was added to the output $yn(k)$ as follows

$$\overline{yn}(k) = yn(k) + \zeta(k),$$

where $\overline{yn}(k)$ is the noisy output and $\zeta(k)$ is a Gaussian-distributed variable. The noise percentage was measured as

$$\text{Porcentaje de ruido } [\%] = \frac{\|\overline{yn}(k)\|_2}{\|yn(k)\|_2} 100,$$

where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the norm applied to a sequence in l_2 . Figure 5.2 shows two plots representing the Lipschitz coefficients evaluated according to equation 4.8 for the noisy output $\overline{yn}(k)$ with 10% Gaussian noise and for $yn(k)$ with 0% noise. In both cases it is easy to see that there is no significant decrease in the Lipschitz coefficients for $m > 7$, indicating a relative robustness of the coefficients with respect to noise. Based on this analysis, the number of Laguerre systems was selected as $m_0 = 7$. The next step in the methodology was to begin training a network with 3 hidden neurons and 7 inputs. Based on the singular value analysis performed with the first 30 values of the training signal, the matrix Σ_0 (see equation 4.16) was obtained

$$\Sigma_0 = \text{diag}\{7.9366, 0.0781, 0.0059\},$$

from which it was determined that one neuron would be sufficient. It should be noted that, given the particular structure of this nonlinear system, one neuron is exactly the correct number the Perceptron should have. It is easy to see that with one neuron the requirements of the nonlinear transformation are covered, so the rest of the approxi-

Figure 5.2: Lipschitz Coefficients for the Discrete Nonlinear System.

mation performed by the LNet structure consists of approximating the linear subsystem using Laguerre systems. The expansion of the linear system in terms of Laguerre systems is now considered. Figure 5.3 illustrates the coefficients scaled by a factor of 2 of the Laguerre system expansion of the linear subsystem and the weights of the hidden layer neuron. In this case, the expansion coefficients are closely related to the weights of the hidden layer neuron. The factor of a factor of 2 that is explained by the difference between the domain $[-1, 1]$ of the sigmoid used in the Perceptron (equation 4.12) and the domain $[0, 1]$ of the nonlinear system function in equation 5.1. It is worth noting that, due to the strong saturation included in the discrete system, it is impossible to approximate the nonlinear system with a linear one: for example, identifying the nonlinear system using Laguerre systems yields a set of oscillatory coefficients that does not converge. The final LNet model was constituted with seven Laguerre systems and a single hidden layer Perceptron with a single neuron. The same data were used for approximation with both the LNet structure and the Korenberg parallel cascade structure. The Korenberg model was fitted according to the procedure defined in Section 2.3.1 under the following assumptions: the number of parallel cascades was limited to 12, since increasing this number yielded only negligible reduction in error; the impulse response length of each linear dynamic system was limited to 30 since no further improvement was obtained beyond this number; the polynomial order was limited to 12 due to numerical insta-

Figure 5.3: Laguerre Expansion Coefficients of the Linear Subsystem and Weights of the Hidden Layer Neuron.

bility in computing polynomial coefficients at higher orders, and within this limit an optimal-order search was implemented. The approximation results can be seen in Figure 5.4, where it is clear that the LNet structure outperforms Korenberg's, achieving an approximation error approximately two orders of magnitude smaller. The model validation results can be seen in Figure 5.5, indicating a good fit of the LNet model. It is easy to see that the correlation $\phi_{\xi\xi}(\tau)$ is a unit impulse while the remaining correlations fall within the 95% confidence limits. This behavior establishes that the residuals cannot be predicted by any linear or nonlinear combination of the inputs and outputs, reflecting a good fit of the LNet model.

5.1.3 Discussion of Results

This example illustrated the capability of the presented modeling methodology to obtain the correct structure of an LNet model for a discrete, time-invariant, causal nonlinear system with fading memory. While the system used does not correspond to any physical system, it does possess an important characteristic present in most real systems: saturation [43, 42]. The presented approximation methodology was applied

Figure 5.4: Approximation and Error of the Discrete Nonlinear System.

to this system, and the approximations obtained by the LNet structure and the Korenberg parallel cascade structure were compared. The approximation results clearly show that the LNet structure outperforms Korenberg's, achieving an approximation error approximately two orders of magnitude smaller. Furthermore, the determination of the fundamental parameters proved relatively robust in the presence of additive output noise, another characteristic commonly found in real systems.

5.2 Echo Cancellation in a Telephone Line

This example demonstrates the advantages of the LNet structure over a Nonlinear FIR in terms of the number of terms required to approximate a given system. This advantage stems from the greater dynamic richness of the LNet structure and manifests for systems that are not themselves a Nonlinear FIR. The comparison is based on an echo cancellation application in a telephone line, whose basic scheme is detailed in Figure 5.6. This example was selected for two reasons. First, it reproduces one presented in [42], allowing comparison of the results obtained. Second, the selected system belongs

Figure 5.5: Validation of the LNet Model for the Discrete Nonlinear System.

to a class that is difficult to approximate using Laguerre systems [6]: the composition $h_2 \circ g_2 \circ h_1 \circ g_1$ of static nonlinear ($g_2(\cdot)$, $g_1(\cdot)$) and linear dynamic ($h_2(s)$, $h_1(s)$) cascade elements, where $g_1(\cdot)$ imposes a severe nonlinearity on the input. This type of operator is difficult to approximate with Laguerre systems because the system essentially contains the nonlinearity at the input while the approximating model has its nonlinearity at the output [6]. Approximation results for various LNet and Nonlinear FIR structures are presented for the system described below.

5.2.1 System Description

Figure 5.6 shows an echo cancellation application at the near-end of a telephone line. The digital signal $r(k)$ at the near-end is converted to analog by the digital-to-analog converter (DAC, represented by the function g_1) and shaped by the linear low-pass transmission filter (with impulse response $h_1(s)$) to produce the analog signal $\tilde{r}(t)$. The hybrid circuit separates $\tilde{r}(t)$ from the signal $s(t)$ received at the far-end, routing $\tilde{r}(t)$ along the transmission line while routing $s(t)$ through the linear reception filter (with impulse response $h_2(s)$) and the sample-and-hold (S/H) device, assumed ideal. Due to losses in the hybrid circuit, the output $\tilde{d}(t)$ contains contributions from $s(t)$ and

an attenuated echo component from $\tilde{r}(t)$. The echo path through the hybrid circuit is represented by the function g_2 , while g_3 represents the far-end signal path. The functions g_1, g_2, g_3, g_4 are static and assumed without hysteresis. The task of the echo canceller

Figure 5.6: Echo Cancellation in a Telephone Line.

$\Sigma(\cdot)$ is to estimate the echo component present in $d(k)$ and cancel it. Neglecting the effects of the far-end signal, the task of the nonlinear echo canceller¹ would be to realize the system $g_4^{-1} \circ h_2(s) \circ g_2 \circ h_1(s) \circ g_1$. Tracking the path of the signal $\tilde{r}(k)$, we can write:

$$\tilde{d}(t) = g_3(s(t)) + g_2(\tilde{r}(t)).$$

If the effects of g_3 are considered negligible, the previous expression can be written as

$$\tilde{d}(t) = s(t) + g_2(\tilde{r}(t)).$$

On the other hand

$$\tilde{r}(t) = h_1 \circ g_1(r(k)),$$

which leads to $\tilde{d}(t) = s(t) + g_2 \circ h_1 \circ g_1(r(k))$, which after the S/H device we write as

$$d(k) = h_2 \circ s(t) + h_2 \circ g_2 \circ h_1 \circ g_1(r(k)).$$

¹A nonlinear echo canceller is necessary when certain attenuation conditions in the hybrid circuit and transmission line make the use of a linear echo canceller impossible [42, p. 747].

The task of the echo canceller can be expressed as $g_4 \circ \Sigma(r(k))$ such that when added to $d(k)$ it can cancel the unwanted echo component expressed by $h_2 \circ g_2 \circ h_1 \circ g_1(r(k))$. Mathematically:

$$d(k) = h_2 \circ s(t) + \overbrace{h_2 \circ g_2 \circ h_1 \circ g_1(r(k)) - g_4 \circ \Sigma(r(k))}^0.$$

Setting this last term to zero (reducing the echo influence), we can obtain the expression for the system that the echo canceller must implement:

$$g_4 \circ \Sigma(r(k)) = h_2 \circ g_2 \circ h_1 \circ g_1(r(k)),$$

from which

$$\Sigma(k) = y(k) = g_4^{-1} \circ h_2 \circ g_2 \circ h_1 \circ g_1(r(k)). \quad (5.2)$$

This nonlinear operator clearly has fading memory, since it results from the cascade composition of static nonlinear functions without hysteresis with linear dynamic systems. For the present example, presented in [42, Example 3, p. 748], the following assumptions are made:

- g_3, g_4 are considered as the identity function.
- $g_1(u) = u^3$, (see Figure 5.7)
- $g_2(u) = 2 \tan^{-1}(5u) + .25u$ (see Figure 5.7)
- $h_1(s) = (s + .75)^{-1}$, transmission filter.
- $h_2(s) = .2(s + .75)^{-1}$, reception filter.

The approximation results of the LNet structure are now compared with those achieved by a delayed-value network.

5.2.2 Approximation Results

It is shown that the LNet structure requires fewer parameters than a Nonlinear FIR or delayed-value network described by equation 2.10, which for simplicity we denote NFIR. Expressed alternatively, this is the same as saying that for Perceptrons with the

Figure 5.7: a) Function g_1 (D/A converter). b) Function g_2 (echo return).

same number of inputs and neurons, the approximation achieved by the LNet structure is superior to that achieved by an NFIR. To demonstrate this, LNet and NFIR structures whose respective Perceptrons have the same number of inputs and hidden neurons are identified. For the LNet structure, the Perceptron inputs are the outputs of the Laguerre filters. For the NFIR structure, they are simply the delayed inputs. For the LNet structure case, the modeling procedure is not followed since the objective is to show the advantages of the structure in terms of economy of terms. The transfer functions of the transmission and reception filters are

$$\begin{aligned} h_1(s) &= (s + .75)^{-1} \\ h_2(s) &= .2(s + .75)^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

admit a discrete approximation that, considering a sampling time $T = 1$, can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} h_1(q^{-1}) &= .5276q^{-1}(1 + .4724q^{-1})^{-1} \\ h_2(q^{-1}) &= .1045q^{-1}(1 + .4724q^{-1})^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

where a pole at .4724 is clearly seen. As a way of demonstrating the robustness of the method with respect to the choice of the Laguerre system pole, this parameter was selected as $a = .49$, close to the pole value .4724 of the filters of equation 5.3. To identify the operator 5.2, an input sequence of 1000 values $\{r(k)\}_{k=1}^{1000}$ was generated based on an EquiProb distribution with change probability $pr = .1$. Applying this sequence to the system and recording its output, a set of values $\{r(k), y(k)\}_{k=1}^{1000}$ was formed, with which

Structure	Systems/Delayed Inputs	Neurons	Error (dB)
<i>LNet</i>	4	7	-12.8151
<i>NFIR</i>	4	7	-5.3284

Table 5.1: Network Structures and Approximation Errors: configuration 1.

various LNet and NFIR structures were trained. First, an LNet structure with four Laguerre systems and a 7-neuron Perceptron was compared with an NFIR structure with four delayed inputs and a 7-neuron Perceptron, as indicated in Table 5.1. The same weight matrices initialized with random values and the same training algorithm were used in both cases. This algorithm was used in both cases for the same number of 100 iterations, after which training was stopped and the approximated outputs were evaluated. The NFIR approximation can be seen in Figure 5.8 and the LNet structure approximation in Figure 5.9. For easier comparison of results, the approximation error was expressed in dB according to the following equation:

$$\text{Error in dB} = 20 \log \left(\frac{\|y - \tilde{y}\|_2}{\|y\|_2} \right),$$

where y is the system output, \tilde{y} the approximated output, and $\|\cdot\|_2$ the norm for sequences in l_2 . From Table 5.1 it can be seen that in this case the LNet structure outperforms the

Figure 5.8: NFir with 4 Inputs and 7 Neurons.

Structure	Systems/Delayed Inputs	Neurons	Error (dB)
<i>LNet</i>	6	15	-20.1111
<i>NFIR</i>	6	15	-9.6584

Table 5.2: Network Structures and Approximation Errors: configuration 2.

Figure 5.9: LNet with 4 Laguerre Systems and 7 Neurons.

NFIR by approximately 7 dB. Repeating the previous procedure for an LNet structure with 6 Laguerre systems and a 15-neuron Perceptron, and for an NFIR structure with 6 delayed inputs and a 15-neuron Perceptron, the data shown in Table ?? were obtained. The approximation results can be seen in Figure 5.10 for the NFIR structure and in Figure 5.11 for the LNet structure. From Table ?? it is easy to see that the LNet structure again outperforms the NFIR by approximately 10 dB. To achieve an approximately equivalent result, an NFIR with 15 inputs and 20 hidden neurons was needed, which contrasts markedly with the 6-input, 15-neuron Perceptron required by the LNet structure. Similar results are shown in Example 2 of [42], where 21 dB rejection is achieved by an NFIR (called a Perceptron Filter) with a 20-input, 50-neuron structure for a simpler finite-memory system.

Figure 5.10: NFIR with 6 Inputs and 15 Neurons.

Figure 5.11: LNet with 6 Laguerre Systems and 15 Neurons.

5.2.3 Discussion of Results

This example demonstrated the advantages of the LNet structure over a Non-linear FIR in terms of the number of terms required to approximate a given system. The comparison was based on an echo cancellation application in a telephone line, a system that is difficult to approximate using Laguerre systems (see [6]). This system was specifically chosen so as not to bias the comparison in favor of either structure. The results were compared with those presented in [42], showing a clear advantage of the LNet structure over NFIR models. The same work [42] also presents the approximation structure of equation 2.11, illustrating its behavior for nonlinear echo cancellation with third- and fifth-order models. This third-order recurrent structure achieves a better approximation (-29 dB) with fewer terms than the LNet structure, but at the cost of a considerably more complex training algorithm.

5.3 Binary Alcohol Distillation Column

In this example the proposed methodology is applied to modeling a binary alcohol distillation column. Additionally, design guidelines are presented for using the column LNet model in a predictive control strategy. Approximation results for both the LNet structure and the Korenberg parallel cascade structure are presented for the column (to enable comparison). It is also shown how the presented modeling ideas can be extended to MISO systems, exemplified by incorporating an additional input into the LNet model resulting from treating the feed flow perturbation as measurable (see Figure 5.12). This MISO LNet model is compared with a linear MISO state-space model. The example concludes with the presentation of a predictive control strategy using the SISO LNet model. The system involved is described below.

5.3.1 System Description

For this study, the dynamic model described in Appendix C, whose bilinear approximation was implemented as in [13], was used. The model was applied to an alcohol separation case assuming constant molar flow and defining a time-invariant relative volatility for each tray. Similar approximation and control results for this binary column were presented in [65]. For the SISO LNet model of this section, the reflux flow rate is

taken as the input and the distillate concentration as the output (see Figure 5.12). For

Figure 5.12: Scheme of the Binary Alcohol Distillation Column.

the system thus considered, Figure 5.13 illustrates how an increase in the reflux flow introduced into the column increases the purity of the distillate product. The figure shows three regions: low purity ($X < .95$), intermediate purity ($.95 \leq X \leq .99$), and high purity ($X > .99$). The system can be approximated by linear models in the low-purity region (tangent line l_1) and in the high-purity region (tangent line l_2), as is easy to see from Figure 5.13. From this figure it is straightforward to conclude that as one moves from the low-purity to the high-purity region, the nonlinear behavior becomes clearly evident. The large difference in the slopes of lines l_1 and l_2 is a concrete manifestation of this behavior. No straight line can approximate the entire range $.95 \leq X \leq .99$ regardless of how it is drawn. This is the reason why a good model in this region is needed; therefore the distillate concentration was approximated for values in $[.94, 1]$. For identification, an input (reflux) sequence of 600 values $\{u(k)\}_{k=1}^{600}$ was generated based on an Equiprob distribution with a change probability $pr = .5$. This signal was appropriately scaled to produce an output (distillate concentration) in the desired range, forming a set of values $\{u(k), y(k)\}_{k=1}^{600}$ of which the first 300 constituted the training set α and the last 300 the validation set β . The output variations in response to input variations were obtained by integrating the differential equation system C.1 with a zero-order hold on the input

Figure 5.13: Steady-State Distillate for Different Reflux Values.

for a sampling period $dt = .01$. The next two sections present the approximation results obtained with the LNet structure and with Korenberg's method.

5.3.2 Approximation Results

Parallel Cascade Model

To obtain the Korenberg parallel cascade model, the procedure defined in Section 2.3.1 was followed under the following assumptions: the number of parallel cascades was limited to 20, since beyond this number only a negligible decrease in error was achieved by adding more cascades; the impulse response length of each linear system was limited to 30 as no further improvements were obtained beyond this number; the system order was limited to 15 due to numerical instability at higher orders. Within this limit an optimal-order search was implemented. The approximation results for the obtained model can be seen in Figure 5.15. Part b) of that figure shows the approximation error for the training set α (with norm $\|Er_\alpha\|_2 = .0161$) and the validation set β (with norm $\|Er_\beta\|_2 = .0489$).

LNet Structure

The first step in the approximation procedure is to estimate the Laguerre system pole a . This pole was evaluated as $a = .55$, since at that value the output of the system $l_0(k)$ best reflects the main time constant of the system. To evaluate the number of Laguerre systems, the procedure of Section 4.2 was followed. The matrix \mathbf{Z} (see equation 4.4) was formed using the input signal filtered by the systems $l_0(k), \dots, l_9(k)$, and the Lipschitz coefficients were then evaluated. The results of this evaluation can be seen in Figure 5.14. It is easy to see that for $m > 5$ there is no significant improvement by adding more systems, so the number of selected systems was $m_0 = 5$. It remains only to define the number of hidden layer neurons. Following the procedure of Section ??, training was started with 30 neurons using only the first 40 samples of the training set α . After some time the training process was stopped and the data matrix \mathbf{Z} was propagated through the hidden layer to obtain the matrix X_0 . The first five singular values of this matrix are shown below, since the remaining ones were practically zero:

$$\Sigma_0 = \text{diag}\{7.9860, 5.0998, 1.9002, 0.1999, 0.0643\}.$$

The number of hidden layer neurons was selected as 5, and training was then completed for the selected structure. The resulting LNet structure consisted of a set of 5 Laguerre systems and a Perceptron with 5 hidden neurons. Part a) of Figure 5.15 illustrates the approximation obtained for the LNet structure. Part b) of that figure shows the approximation error for the training set α (with norm $\|Er_\alpha\|_2 = .0034$) and the validation set β (with norm $\|Er_\beta\|_2 = .012$). As the final step, the LNet structure was validated; the results are illustrated in Figure 5.16. It is easy to see that the correlation $\phi_{\xi\xi}(\tau)$ is a unit impulse while the remaining correlations fall within the 95% confidence limits. This behavior establishes that the residuals cannot be predicted by any linear or nonlinear combination of inputs and outputs. It is readily verified that the obtained LNet model is valid and substantially improves on the results obtained with the parallel cascade structure. The following shows an example of how the LNet structure can be extended to consider MISO systems.

Figure 5.14: Lipschitz Coefficients for the Column.

Figure 5.15: Distillate Approximation by SISO LNet and Parallel Cascade Models.

Figure 5.16: Validation of the LNet Model for the Column.

Figure 5.17: Proposed MISO Extension for the LNet Structure.

MISO Column Model

The LNet model was expanded by incorporating a second input $u_2(k)$ in the scheme shown in Figure 5.17. The conception of a MISO LNet model proved to be useful in practice, even though a formal proof of its approximation capabilities remains to be formulated. To build the MISO LNet model, five Laguerre systems (with $a_1 = .55$) related to the reflux input $u_1(k)$ and two Laguerre systems (with $a_2 = 0$) related to the feed flow perturbation input $u_2(k)$ (considered measurable) were used. The resulting LNet model consisted of 7 Laguerre systems and a Perceptron with 9 hidden neurons. To compare the obtained results, a third-order linear state-space model identified using the Matlab Identification Toolbox was used. Figure 5.18 shows the approximation results of both models. The figure presents the variations produced in the distillate with respect to variations in the reflux (lower left scale) and percentage variations in the feed flow rate (lower right scale). It is easy to see that the LNet structure outperforms the linear model in approximation quality over the entire approximation domain. Aspects related to predictive control are developed below.

Figure 5.18: MISO LNet and Linear Models for the Column.

5.3.3 General Aspects of Predictive Control

The main characteristic of predictive control schemes is the explicit use of a dynamic model of the system to evaluate the effects of future control actions on the system outputs. Among the particular applications that can be cited are the “Dynamic Matrix Control” [25] and “Algorithmic Model Control” [21] algorithms. In both cases, the control action at time t results from minimizing a certain performance index that may involve states, outputs, and inputs, as well as constraints on some of them. Particular applications using neural network models can be found in [18] and [25], while in [19] a wavelet-based model was used. These implementations are based on NARMAX-type schemes as in Section 2.3.2. In [12], models based on Recurrent Neural Networks were used; in that work a recurrent network models the nonlinear function relating states to their derivatives, assuming all states are measurable. For the case where states are not measurable, [45] proposes the use of nonlinear observers. However, all the schemes mentioned are of great complexity, requiring prolonged training times to obtain the models.

In [44] the problem of so-called Receding Horizon Control of nonlinear systems expressed in state variables is addressed. The problem is stated as that of controlling the state x of the system at time t by determining the control input u^o that solves a constrained optimal control problem over the interval $[t, t + T]$. The constrained optimal control problem is usually formulated as the minimization of a quadratic functional over $[t, t + T]$ subject to $x(t + T) = 0$. The parameter T is chosen to be greater than the maximum time required to bring the system from any state to the origin. The constraint $x(t + T) = 0$ imposed at time T ensures stability [44]. As suggested in [44], the control problem can also be discretized in time to reduce the optimal control problem to a finite-dimensional nonlinear programming problem. We now show how LNet models can be used in predictive control strategies.

LNet Predictive Control

The control problem is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min & \sum_{j=1}^T \|y_{t+j} - yd_{t+j}\|^2 m_j + \sum_{j=1}^{T_1} \|\Delta u_{t+j-1}\|^2 n_j, \\ \text{st } & \Delta u_j = u_j - u_{j-1} = 0, \quad j = T_1, \dots, T \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

where $\{u_t\}$, $\{y_t\}$, $\{yd_t\}$ are the input, output, and reference sequences respectively. The control action Δu at time t is chosen as the first element of the solution sequence $\{u_t^o, \dots, u_{t+N_1-1}^o\}$ of the previous optimization problem. The sequences m_j and n_j are used to adjust the control characteristics. Mayne [44] suggested that T should be selected as a value greater than the settling time of the system to provide a certain degree of stability to the control problem. In the LNet model formulation, the dynamic part is linear and is represented by the Laguerre systems. The dominant dynamic behavior is due to the highest-order Laguerre system $l_n(k)$ used in the model. One way to bound the time horizon T is to approximate $l_n(k)$ by its first N terms, as if it were a FIR, assuming that the contribution of higher-order terms is negligible, and then take $T > N$. Let $G_n u$ (equation 3.12) be the response of $l_n(k)$ to input u considering the infinite impulse response of $l_n(k)$, and let $G_n^N u$ be the approximation to $G_n u$ using the first N terms of the impulse response of $l_n(k)$. To bound T , we evaluate the ratio $|G_n^N u| / |G_n u|$, which tends to one as $N \rightarrow \infty$. It is then necessary to select an N for which this ratio is approximately equal to 1 and take $T > N$. Setting $G_n v = 0$ in equations 3.13 and 3.12 it can be shown that

$$\frac{|G_n^N u|}{|G_n u|} \leq 1 - 2r^N + r^{N+1}, \quad (5.5)$$

where $|a| < |r| < 1$. The value of r is selected to bound the magnitude of the pole a . Since this value is less than 1, it is easy to see that as $N \rightarrow \infty$ —i.e., when all terms of the impulse response are taken—the ratio of equation 5.5 tends to unity, as illustrated in Figure 5.19. This shows a lower bound on the dominant dynamic behavior considering only the first N terms of $l_n(k)$. This provides a means for evaluating the required T , simply by selecting the value of $T > N$ for which ratio 5.5 approaches unity. We now see how the SISO LNet model of the previous section is applied in this predictive control scheme. This model consists of 5 Laguerre systems with pole $a = .55$. Figure 5.19 shows the lower bound on the control horizon evaluated for a pole $a = .55$ and $r = .56$. From the preceding analysis it is easy to see that $T > 14$ must be selected to ensure a certain degree of stability; the selected control horizon was $T = 15$. To compare the control results using the LNet model, a third-order linear discrete state-space model was identified using the MATLABTM identification toolbox. The same predictive control algorithm was used with both models, tested by controlling the system at three different operating points subject to various perturbations in the feed flow rate. The desired

Figure 5.19: Control Horizon Bound for the Column.

Model	Horizon T	Sequence m_j	Sequence n_j
<i>Linear</i>	15	10	.05
<i>LNet</i>	15	10	.01

Table 5.3: Parameters Used in the Control Algorithm.

composition profile yd was determined by the following difference equation:

$$yd(k) = .4u(k) + .6yd(k-1),$$

where yd is the desired distillate concentration and u is the reflux (manipulated variable). The control algorithm parameters of equation 5.4 are shown in Table 5.3 for the linear and LNet models. The results of using both models in the predictive control strategy previously discussed can be seen in Figure 5.20. The figure shows the system operating at three distinct regions defined by distillate purities of .992, .962, and .977, forcing the system to traverse its region of maximum nonlinearity. The same figure shows the perturbations introduced in the feed flow rate, whose percentage level is shown on the lower right scale. It can be seen from Table 5.3 that the sequence n_j had to be increased for the linear model, since with a linear model it was impossible to achieve faster control

without oscillations. From the figure it is clear that the control achieved with the LNet model outperforms that achieved with the linear model.

Figure 5.20: Column Control Results.

5.3.4 Discussion of Results

In this example the proposed methodology was applied to modeling a binary alcohol distillation column. The obtained LNet model was compared with Korenberg's parallel cascade structure; this comparison was favorable to the LNet structure. It was also shown how the presented modeling ideas can be extended to MISO systems, demonstrated by reformulating the column LNet model to incorporate an additional input. This MISO LNet model was compared with a linear MISO state-space model, and the example concluded with the presentation of a predictive control strategy using the SISO LNet model.

5.4 Conclusions

This chapter presented several examples illustrating specific aspects of the developed modeling methodology. The first example demonstrated the capability of the presented modeling methodology to find the correct structure for a discrete, time-invariant, causal nonlinear system with fading memory. The second presented a case of nonlinear echo cancellation to illustrate the advantages of the LNet structure over a Nonlinear FIR regarding the number of terms required to approximate a given system. The last example considered the application of the proposed methodology to modeling a binary alcohol distillation column; the modeling aspect considered a MISO extension. Additionally, design guidelines for using LNet models in a predictive control strategy were presented.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Recommendations

This thesis presented the LNet approximation structure for discrete nonlinear systems. The exposition began with the problem of system approximation, particularly oriented toward the identification of nonlinear input-output models. From the wide variety of such models, those with a sound theoretical foundation and representative of their class were selected. Among the traditional models cited were the Volterra series, the Wiener series, the cascade block model, and Korenberg's parallel cascade block model. The latter was chosen for comparison with the LNet structure because it overcomes most of the difficulties presented by the earlier models and because of its simplicity of use. With equal criterion, the neural-network-based models were selected: the delayed-values network model and the NARMAX model. In this case the selection proved difficult due to the great diversity of existing neural network models and, in many cases, the lack of results ensuring that a given model is capable of approximating a system with given characteristics. In this sense, the present thesis aims to contribute by characterizing the systems that can be approximated by the LNet structure and by developing a methodology for its identification. The classical delayed-inputs structure or nonlinear FIR was chosen from the neural network models for comparison with the LNet structure. The concepts of neuron, layer, and topology were defined, together with a general framework for specifying discrete nonlinear systems that incorporate neural networks. It should be noted that while this framework is sufficiently general to include a wide diversity of neural network models, it does not accommodate those in which the concept of layer cannot be developed. This framework was used to define the LNet structure.

The LNet structure is composed of a set of discrete Laguerre systems nonlinearly

combined by a single hidden layer Perceptron. While this scheme is similar to Wiener's, it differs from it principally in the use of a single hidden layer Perceptron. This Perceptron, the characteristic element of the LNet structure, is what allows practically realizable approximations to be obtained. Comparing the LNet structure with the original Wiener scheme, it is easy to see that the Perceptron replaces the Hermite polynomials. It was shown that the number of coefficients involved in the Wiener scheme grows exponentially with the model dimensions: assuming 10 Laguerre systems and a Hermite polynomial of order 2, on the order of 2^{10} coefficients would be required. Results were presented demonstrating the advantage of using neural networks as universal approximators of nonlinear functions rather than other types of approximators such as polynomials. It was proved that the LNet structure is capable of approximating discrete, causal, time-invariant, nonlinear operators possessing fading memory. To prove the approximation capabilities of the LNet structure, the necessary concepts were defined, among which fading memory plays a central role. It was shown that this concept can be viewed as a certain form of continuity of the operator associated with the system. It should be noted that few results are available that establish under what conditions a dynamic system possesses fading memory; this problem is currently the subject of ongoing research.

The thesis continued with the presentation of the methodology for determining the LNet structure. The expansion pole was determined assuming that the dominant time constant of the system is available or easy to evaluate. Alternatively, this pole can be estimated by approximating in some sense the system response to an excitation sequence, using the low-pass section of the Laguerre systems. The remaining structure parameters are the number of Laguerre systems and the number of neurons in the hidden layer. The use of the so-called Lipschitz coefficients, whose application is grounded in the continuity of the LNet operator, has proved to be a useful instrument for evaluating the number of Laguerre systems. From a practical standpoint, a means is available for bounding the number of Laguerre systems based on the available information. For estimating the number of hidden layer neurons, a variation of pruning techniques was used. This technique is based on a singular value decomposition of the data matrix propagated through the hidden layer. Finally, the procedures required to validate the obtained model were presented. Some remarks are in order regarding certain modeling aspects.

One of these concerns the use of Laguerre systems when the system to be modeled is highly oscillatory. It is known that even in linear cases, this problem leads to slow convergence of the Laguerre model coefficients. A possible solution would be to use Kautz series [76]. These series are orthogonal, but unlike Laguerre series they are generated from a single complex pole, which allows a linear system to be expressed as a sum of orthogonal second-order sections. Another possible basis for expressing a highly oscillatory system consists of certain orthogonal second-order sections generated by different poles, as in [14]. The drawback with both methods is that when applied to nonlinear models, their training algorithms would become excessively complicated, since the pole values and Perceptron parameters would need to be estimated jointly. A further remark concerns the obtained model: due to the way it is evaluated, it is not optimal in the sense of the number of parameters it comprises. However, when properly validated, it presents a reasonable alternative to recurrent schemes, balancing the training effort against the structural determination effort.

The presented methodology was illustrated through several examples highlighting specific facets of the modeling strategy. The first example demonstrated the capability of the modeling methodology to find the correct structure for a discrete, time-invariant, causal nonlinear system possessing fading memory. The approximation obtained by the LNet structure substantially outperformed that obtained by Korenberg's parallel cascade structure. This experiment contains two elements commonly found in practice: the presence of noise and saturation. The capability of determining the LNet structure in the presence of output measurement noise was evaluated. When data contain noise, it is advisable to use a robust back-error propagation algorithm [11]. This technique was applied with notable success by Sánchez et al. [59] in estimating certain relationships between variables of an ethylene cracking furnace using real data containing measurement noise and gross errors. The algorithm is relatively insensitive to parameter overfitting, which suggests an interesting alternative: starting the LNet structure fitting with an over-abundant number of Laguerre systems and applying a pruning technique to obtain realizations with fewer parameters. This approach will be the subject of future investigations. The second example presented a case of nonlinear echo cancellation in a telephone line to illustrate the advantages of the LNet structure over a Nonlinear FIR in terms of the number of terms needed to approximate a given system. In this case, the

substantially smaller number of parameters required by the LNet structure compared to the Nonlinear FIR was demonstrated. Furthermore, the accuracy of the approximation results obtained for the Nonlinear FIR was contrasted with previously published results. The last example considered the application of the proposed methodology to modeling a binary alcohol distillation column. The approximation results obtained were compared with those of Korenberg's parallel cascade structure, with the LNet structure results proving substantially better. In this example, a MISO extension of the presented methodology was considered. The approximation capabilities of the MISO LNet structure were shown to exceed those obtained with a linear model. Obtaining theoretical results establishing the approximation capabilities of the LNet structure for MISO and MIMO systems will be the subject of future investigations. Additionally, design guidelines were presented that

allow the use of LNet models in predictive control strategies. Two possible subjects of study for future lines of research in control-related aspects should be noted. One is the determination of stability conditions for predictive control strategies using LNet models. Another interesting aspect worth careful study is the application of techniques from differential algebra to discrete nonlinear models. Preliminary partial results indicate that it is possible to obtain a discrete approximation of a continuous nonlinear system, and then apply input-output linearization techniques [37] using the obtained model. Proceeding in this way, it would be possible to use a discrete LNet model identified from input-output data to linearize the continuous system.

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Appendix A

Properties of Laguerre Systems

Some properties of the set of Laguerre systems $L_n(\mathfrak{z})$, defined by equation 1.15 for $nd = 1$, with their time-domain counterpart $l_n(k) = \mathcal{Z}^{-1}[L_n(\mathfrak{z})]$, are presented below.

A) *The set of systems is exponentially stable.*

The systems can be expressed in the transform domain as $L_n(\mathfrak{z}) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l_n(k) \mathfrak{z}^{-k}$ for $|a| < 1$, which implies that the series is absolutely convergent for $|\mathfrak{z}| > |a|$. Selecting $\mathfrak{z} = \mathfrak{z}_1$ such that $|a| < |\mathfrak{z}_1| < 1$ implies the convergence of $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} |l_n(k) \mathfrak{z}_1^{-k}| < \infty$. Since the series is absolutely convergent, there exists a finite constant A such that $|l_n(k) \mathfrak{z}_1^{-k}| < A$. A possible choice to bound $|l_n(k)|$ is to take $A = n + 1$ and $r = |\mathfrak{z}_1|$, from which

$$|l_n(k)| < (n + 1) r^k. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

With this choice of r , $|a| < |r| < 1$, $|l_n(k)|$ must approach 0 at least exponentially as $n \rightarrow \infty$. \square

B) The set of Laguerre systems is orthonormal, i.e., the following holds:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l_p(k) l_q(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & p \neq q \\ 1 & p = q \end{cases}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

This property can be proved using Parseval's relation for discrete systems [53,

p. 66], starting from

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l_p(k) l_q(k) = \frac{1}{2\pi j} \oint_C L_p(z) L_q(z^{-1}) z^{-1} dz, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where $j = \sqrt{-1}$, $L_n(z)$ is given by equation 1.15, and $l_n(k)$ is the inverse transform of $L_n(z)$. To select the contour C , the region of integration must be considered, determined by the poles of $L_p(z) L_q(z^{-1}) z^{-1}$. The poles of $L_p(z)$ are at $z = a$, while those of $L_q(z^{-1})$ are at $z = a^{-1}$; therefore, choosing $C : |z| = 1$ places us in the region of convergence $a < |z| < a^{-1}$, where $|z|$ denotes the modulus of z . Substituting the values of $L_n(z)$ from 1.15 into A.3 gives

$$\frac{1}{2\pi j} \oint_C L_p(z) L_q(z^{-1}) z^{-1} dz = \frac{1}{2\pi j} \oint_C 1 - a^2 \frac{z}{z - a} \left(\frac{1 - az}{z - a} \right)^p \frac{z^{-1}}{z^{-1} - a} \left(\frac{1 - az^{-1}}{z^{-1} - a} \right)^q z^{-1} dz$$

Grouping terms

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l_p(k) l_q(k) = \frac{1 - a^2}{2\pi j} \oint_C \frac{1}{z - a} \frac{1}{1 - az} \left(\frac{z - a}{1 - az} \right)^{q-p} dz, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

we arrive at the desired expression, which must be evaluated for the cases $p = q$ and $p \neq q$.

$p = q$: In this case it is necessary to evaluate the integral of equation A.4 for $p = q$:

$$\oint_C \frac{1}{z - a} \frac{1}{1 - az} dz, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

which is evaluated using Cauchy's Residue Theorem. The contour C must enclose the region of convergence $a < |z| < 1/a$, so that there is only one pole $z = a$. The residue of equation A.5 computed at $z = a$ equals $2\pi j/(1 - a^2)$, from which, by equation A.4, it is proved that

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l_p(k) l_p(k) = 1.$$

$p \neq q$: In this case it is necessary to evaluate the integral of equation A.4 for $p \neq q$.

Suppose $q > p$ (the case $q < p$ is symmetric):

$$\oint_C \frac{1}{(1 - a\mathfrak{z})(1 - a\mathfrak{z})^{q-p}} d\mathfrak{z}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

It is easy to see that integral A.6 has no poles inside the region of integration $a < |\mathfrak{z}| < 1/a$. Therefore the residue is zero, from which by equation A.4 it is proved that for $p \neq q$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l_p(k) l_q(k) = 0.$$

□

Appendix B

Lemma I

Lemma 4. Consider the norm $\|u\|_w$ defined by equation 3.5 in the space $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$. Then, given $m_1 > 0$, the space

$$\mathbf{K}_- \triangleq \{u \in l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-) \mid \|u\|_\infty \leq m_1\} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

equipped with the norm $\|u\|_w$ is compact.

Proof. We must show that the space \mathbf{K}_- with the norm $\|u\|_w$ is compact in $l^\infty(\mathbb{Z}_-)$. To this end we choose any sequence $\{u_n\}$ in \mathbf{K}_- with $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. It is a known result that the space l^∞ of bounded sequences equipped with the norm $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ is not compact [31]. However, the restriction of \mathbf{K}_- to $[-n, 0]$, denoted $\mathbf{K}_-[-n, 0]$, is compact since it is a set of finite values for each n , uniformly bounded by m_1 . To prove the compactness of \mathbf{K}_- , we proceed to find a $u_0 \in \mathbf{K}_-$ and a subsequence of $\{u_n\}$ that converges to u_0 in the norm $\|\cdot\|_w$. Let \mathbb{N} be the set of natural numbers. Since by hypothesis $|u_n(0)| \leq m_1$, it is possible to find $u_0(0) \in \mathbf{K}_-[0]$ and an infinite subset $\mathbb{N}_0 \subset \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$|u_n(0) - u_0(0)| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}_0.$$

Considering $\{u_n \mid n \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$ as a sequence in $\mathbf{K}_-[-1, 0]$, it can be concluded that there exists $u_0(-1) \in \mathbf{K}_-[-1, 0]$ and an infinite subset $\mathbb{N}_1 \subset \mathbb{N}_0$ such that

$$\sup_{-1 \leq k \leq 0} |u_n(k) - u_0(k)| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}_1.$$

Continuing this argument, we find $u_0 \in \mathbf{K}_-$ and a decreasing sequence of infinite

subsets $\mathbb{N}_0 \supset \mathbb{N}_1 \supset \mathbb{N}_2 \cdots$ such that for each m

$$\sup_{-m \leq k \leq 0} |u_n(k) - u_0(k)| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}_m. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

We now apply a diagonal argument to take an increasing sequence n_m such that $n_m \in \mathbb{N}_m$, i.e., for each k the subsequences that converge to $u_0(k)$ are selected. Then by equation B.2, for each m_0 we have

$$\sup_{-m_0 \leq k \leq 0} |u_{n_m}(k) - u_0(k)| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty,$$

which means that the sequence u_{n_m} converges pointwise to u_0 on compact subsets.

It remains to show that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \|u_{n_m} - u_0\|_w = 0$, i.e., that u_{n_m} converges to u_0 in the norm $\|u\|_w$. Since the weight sequence satisfies $w(k) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$, it is possible to find $m_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $w(m_0) \leq \epsilon/2M_1$, with $\epsilon > 0$; and since $u_{n_m}, u_0 \in \mathbf{K}_-$,

$$\sup_{k \leq -m_0} |u_{n_m}(k) - u_0(k)| w(-k) \leq 2M_1 w(m_0) < \epsilon. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Now find m_1 such that

$$\sup_{-m_0 \leq k \leq 0} |u_{n_m}(k) - u_0(k)| \leq \epsilon, \quad \text{for } m \geq m_1. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Then by equations B.3 and B.4, and since $w(k) \leq 1$, we conclude that

$$\|u_{n_m} - u_0\|_w \leq \epsilon, \quad \text{for } m \geq m_1.$$

The weighted norm $\|\cdot\|_w$ acts in such a way as to make the subspace \mathbf{K}_- appear compact. We saw that equipped with the norm $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ this subspace is not compact, but it is compact when restricted to $\mathbf{K}_-[-n, 0]$. The weighted norm $\|\cdot\|_w$ makes \mathbf{K}_- compact by producing a vanishing of the tail of the sequence, which is equivalent to saying that it weights the sequence in such a way that it behaves as if it were $\mathbf{K}_-[-n, 0]$. This concludes the proof of the Lemma. \square

Appendix C

Model of the Binary Alcohol Distillation Column

The model of the n -plate distillation column schematized in Figure 5.12 is presented below, with the following definitions:

x_k, z_k : liquid and vapor concentrations on the k -th tray.

M_k : vapor-liquid equilibrium coefficient on the k -th tray.

L_k : liquid flow rate on the k -th tray.

V_k : vapor flow rate on the k -th tray.

L_F : feed liquid flow rate.

X_F : feed liquid concentration.

H : liquid holdup on a tray.

H_D : liquid holdup in the condenser.

H_B : liquid holdup in the reboiler.

On each tray there exists a nonlinear vapor-liquid equilibrium relationship given by

$$M_k = \frac{\alpha_k}{1 + (\alpha_k - 1) x_k},$$

where α_k is the relative volatility for the k -th tray, assumed constant. In the condenser section, the mass balance equations, taking tray 1 as the top tray, are

$$V_2 z_2 - L_1 x_1 - (V_2 - L_1) x_1 = H_D \dot{x}_1 .$$

Taking $V_2 = V$ constant for all elements and expressing the vapor concentration in terms of the liquid concentration, $z_2 = M_2 x_2$, gives

$$\dot{x}_1 = \frac{V}{H_D} (M_2 x_2 - x_1) .$$

For a tray in the rectifying section, considering that the feed enters at tray k ,

$$L_{i-1} x_{i-1} - L_i x_i + V_{i+1} z_{i+1} - V_i z_i = H_i \dot{x}_i ,$$

and using $z_i = M_i x_i$, $L_i = L$, $V_i = V$, $H_i = H$, we obtain

$$\dot{x}_i = \frac{1}{H} [L (x_{i-1} - x_i) + V (M_{i+1} x_{i+1} - M_i x_i)] ,$$

for $i : 1, \dots, k - 1$. Finally,

$$\dot{x}_k = \frac{1}{H} [L (x_{k-1} - x_k) + V (M_{k+1} x_{k+1} - M_k x_k) + L_F (x_F - x_k)]$$

$$\dot{x}_j = \frac{1}{H} [L (x_{j-1} - x_j) + V (M_{j+1} x_{j+1} - M_j x_j) + L_F (x_{j-1} - x_j)]$$

for $j : k + 1, \dots, n - 1$. The last tray is then modeled as

$$\dot{x}_n = \frac{1}{H_b} [L (x_{n-1} - x_n) + V x_n - M_n x_n + L_F (x_{n-1} - x_n)]$$

In summary, the set of differential equations modeling the system is:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \dot{x}_1 = \frac{V}{H_D} (M_2 x_2 - x_1) \\ \vdots \\ \dot{x}_i = \frac{1}{H} [L(x_{i-1} - x_i) + V(M_{i+1} x_{i+1} - M_i x_i)] \quad \text{for } i : 1, \dots, k-1 \\ \dot{x}_k = \frac{1}{H} [L(x_{k-1} - x_k) + V(M_{k+1} x_{k+1} - M_k x_k) + L_F(x_F - x_k)] \\ \dot{x}_j = \frac{1}{H} [L(x_{j-1} - x_j) + V(M_{j+1} x_{j+1} - M_j x_j) + L_F(x_{j-1} - x_j)] \quad \text{for } j : k+1, \dots, n-1 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{x}_n = \frac{1}{H_b} [L(x_{n-1} - x_n) + V x_n - M_n x_n + L_F(x_{n-1} - x_n)] \end{array} \right.$$

Defining the system state vector as $x = [x_1, \dots, x_n]^T$, and inputs and outputs as

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{L}{H} \\ \frac{V}{H} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_n \end{bmatrix},$$

respectively, and in normalized form for L_F and X_F ,

$$\begin{bmatrix} w_1 \\ w_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{L_F}{H} \\ \frac{L_F X_F}{H} \end{bmatrix},$$

the system in its final form is

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \dot{x} = g(x) u + p(x) w \\ y = h(x) \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

X_F	L_F	V	L	H	H_D	H_B
.5	250	260	145	.45	3.941	4.628

Table C.1: Column Parameters

For the present example $n = 10$ and $k = 5$, so that

$$g(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & (M_2x_2 - x_1) \frac{H}{H_D} \\ x_1 - x_2 & M_3x_3 - M_2x_2 \\ x_2 - x_3 & M_4x_4 - M_3x_3 \\ x_3 - x_4 & M_5x_5 - M_4x_4 \\ x_4 - x_5 & M_6x_6 - M_5x_5 \\ x_5 - x_6 & M_7x_7 - M_6x_6 \\ x_6 - x_7 & M_8x_8 - M_7x_7 \\ x_7 - x_8 & M_9x_9 - M_8x_8 \\ x_8 - x_9 & M_{10}x_{10} - M_9x_9 \\ (x_9 - x_{10}) \frac{H}{H_B} & (x_{10} - M_{10}x_{10}) \frac{H}{H_B} \end{bmatrix}, \quad p(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ -x_6 & 1 \\ x_6 - x_7 & 0 \\ x_7 - x_8 & 0 \\ x_8 - x_9 & 0 \\ (x_9 - x_{10}) \frac{H}{H_B} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$h(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_{10} \end{bmatrix}$$

for the following relative volatility values $\alpha = [0, 4.5, 4.2, 4, 3.8, 3, 2.9, 2.7, 2.6, 2.6]^T$